

RM ROADMAP

D2.1 Preliminary report on professional development opportunities

This report provides a first overview of existing professional development opportunities targeting Research Managers (RMs). Five categories were defined to collect the data mainly focused on opportunities targeting RMs: Training, Mobility, Networking, Funding opportunities, and RM Networks.

WP2, Training and Development, NOVA University Lisbon (NOVA)

RM-ROADMAP project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement number 101058475.

RM Roadmap_NOVA_WP2_D2.1_Preliminary report on professional development

Project full
title

**“Creating Framework Conditions for Research Management to Strengthen
the European Research Area”**

Project
acronym RM
Roadmap

Grant Agreement no.

101058475

D2.1: Preliminary report on professional
development opportunities

Copyright by the RM Roadmap consortium

RM Roadmap_NOVA_WP2_D2.1_Preliminary report on professional development

Authors:	Cristina Oliveira, Lia Neves, Margarida Trindade, Ana Carrapato, Diana Delgado and Carolina Varela
Reviewer(s):	Borana Taraj, Erica Feliziani, Karl Kerschbaum, Marta Agostinho, Virág Zsár, Blanka Csité, Andjela Pepic
Dissemination level [*] :	PU
Submission date:	31.08.2023
Start date of project:	September 1 st , 2022
Duration of the project:	36 months
Organisation name of lead contractor for this deliverable:	NOVA

*This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101058475

PU – Public (fully open, automatically posted online on the Project Result platforms);

SE – Sensitive (limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement);

CO – EU classified: EU restricted, EU confidential, EU secret under Decision 2015/444.

RM Roadmap_NOVA_WP2_D2.1_Preliminary report on professional development

Document metadata

Version	Date	Modification reason	Modified by
1.0	28-06-2023	First draft	Cristina Oliveira, Lia Neves, Margarida Trindade, Ana Carrapato, Diana Delgado and Carolina Varela
2.0	28-07-2023	Final version	Cristina Oliveira, Lia Neves, Margarida Trindade, Ana Carrapato, Diana Delgado and Carolina Varela

Contents

1. Introduction	4
1.1 About the RM Roadmap.....	4
1.2 Work Package 2 - Training and Development.....	5
2. Background.....	7
2.1 Research Managers (RMs) within the R&I Ecosystem	7
2.2 Research Managers: main skills and competencies	9
2.3 The role of RM professional associations in providing opportunities for professional development.....	10
2.4 RM Roadmap contribution to RMs professional development	12
3. Methodology.....	14
4. Preliminary Results.....	17
4.1 Training Opportunities	18
4.2 Mobility and Networking Opportunities	21
4.3 RM associations and communities of practice across Europe	24
4.4 Funding Opportunities	24
5. Challenges Encountered.....	25
6. Conclusions	25
7. References.....	27
Annex 1 - WP 2 Concept Note	
Annex 2 - WP 2 Online Template	
Annex 3 - WP 2 Opportunity Typology	

Summary

Following and feeding one of RM Roadmap's main objectives - inform the community about existing training, networking, funding, and mobility opportunities - the aim of this preliminary report is to present a first overview of existing professional development opportunities targeting Research Managers (RMs). Five categories were defined to collect the data mainly focused on opportunities targeting RMs: Training, Mobility, Networking, and Funding opportunities. The fifth category is RM Associations, as they often provide a combination of the above-mentioned activities. Mapping the RMs associations and networks will also be relevant to feed in Task 2.4 - Fostering national and thematic communities (in Widening Countries), expected to start in August 2023.

In this preliminary report, we present the information collected during the last 6 months of the project based on the literature review, desk research, and the direct contributions from RMs and a multitude of different institutions' own information. The collected information will be complemented by the RM Roadmap survey (expected to be launched in September 2023) and disseminated to all RM community through an open online tool, developed in collaboration with the parallel EU Project CARDEA (D 2.2 - Online tool for professional development opportunities (Aug 2024). The final Report on the professional development opportunities (Jun 2025) will shed light on the state-of-art of these opportunities and produce recommendations for future Europe-wide professional development schemes in order to better inform and influence policy development on the next steps.

The report is structured in seven sections as follows: section 1) introduces the RM ROADMAP project and work package 2 (WP2); section 2) on background about the skills and competencies of Research Managers and their roles in the Research and Innovation ecosystem; section 3) methodology; section 4) on the preliminary results of the mapping exercise on the development opportunities; section 5) challenges encountered section 6) with conclusions. This report includes additionally three annexes composed of the concept note, which describes the planned activities for WP2, the online template used to collect the information, and a synthesis of the collected information by opportunity typology, crossing geographical coverage with the different opportunities.

1. Introduction

1.1 About the RM Roadmap

RM Roadmap will chart a course for the future of research management (RM) in Europe and foster a community to support its delivery. It will be conducted over 36 months funded to the amount of €1.5m by the European Commission Horizon Europe funding programme.

The overarching objective of RM Roadmap is to identify and adapt the research management capital base of the EU, including the widening countries, and emerging needs of its current and future research management workforce to improve the EU's competitiveness and sustain its economic performance.

RM Roadmap will allow existing European networks to connect on a smart community platform which will enable an unprecedented consultation process in research management. This co-creation process will gather the existing communities and expand upon them to reach two main objectives: to create and inform a bottom-up consensus on the future of RM in a roadmap, and to inform the community about existing training, networking, funding, and career mobility opportunities.

Eight partners are working together on this project: European Association of Research Managers and Administrators (Belgium); HETFA Research Institute (Hungary); Nova University Lisbon (Portugal); Association of European Science & Technology Transfer Professionals (Netherlands); Crowdhelix Limited (Ireland), The Cyprus Institute (Cyprus) and associated partners Janssen Pharmaceuticals (J&J) and Una Europa (Belgium).

For the implementation of the project, the following Work Packages were considered:

WP	Work Package name	Lead partner	Deliverables
WP1	Intelligence	HETFA	D1.1, D1.2
WP2	Training and Development	NOVA	D2.1 - "Preliminary Report on professional development opportunities" D2.2 - "Online tool for professional development opportunities" D2.3 - "Report on the professional development opportunities"

WP3	Roadmap and Advocacy	EARMA	D3.3, D3.2, D3.4, D3.1
WP4	Community, Communication and Dissemination	Crowdhelix	D4.5, D4.1, D4.2, D4.6, D4.4, D4.3
WP5	Project Management	EARMA	D5.2, D5.1, D5.4, D5.3
WP6	Sustainability and Exploitation	ASTP	D6.2, D6.1

1.2 Work Package 2 - Training and Development

The overall objective of Work Package 2 (WP2) in the RM ROADMAP project is to map existing training, networking, mobility, and funding opportunities to the Research Management community across Europe, showcase these opportunities available in an open online tool, and foster collaboration, exchange of resources and best practices between the RM trainers and communities of practice.

For that, the following tasks were defined:

- Task 2.1 - Assessing the current training, networking, mobility, and funding opportunities for the RM community & creating an open smart database
- Task 2.2 - Producing survey, gap analysis, and recommendations to fulfil the identified training and networking needs
- Task 2.3 - Fostering the creation of communities of practice among trainers
- Task 2.4 - Fostering national and thematic communities (in Widening Countries) including research infrastructure: RM community incubator.

For a complete overview of the WP2 tasks, activity plan, and calendarization, please explore WP2 Concept Note in Annex 1. This concept note was created to make WP2 thorough planning and efficient operationalization easier. To assure the effective execution of the work package, we established the major strategies, tasks, and deadlines. This concept paper acts as a thorough blueprint, offering a distinct structure and rules for all parties engaged in putting WP2 into action.

Task 2.1 will map the current opportunities for RM professional development, namely training, networking, mobility, and funding. The objective of this collection of data is two-fold:

RM Roadmap_NOVA_WP2_D2.1_Preliminary report on professional development

Objective 1: to develop an online tool, user-friendly and openly available to all RM as a single-entry point for obtaining the most relevant information about training, mobility, networking, and funding opportunities in Europe, country by country, and organized by type of opportunity.

- with it, we aim to close the gap between practitioners and key resources for professional development, improving information accessibility within the RM community. The online tool will give RM professionals the ability to investigate various possibilities for professional development and find the most pertinent ones to improve their knowledge and competencies.

Objective 2: The currently available opportunities (task 2.1) will be compared with the needs identified by the RM community via the RM Roadmap survey (task 2.2) to understand the existing gaps in training, mobility, networking, and funding necessary for RM professional development in Europe. Recommendations for new schemes for professional development will be discussed with the RM community and integrated into the overall roadmap for the RM System in Europe.

It is not our aim to develop new training schemes as part of the RM Roadmap project but rather to foster the development of communities of practice of trainers that will exchange best practices, lessons learned and teaching tools with the RM community (task 2.3 and 2.4). This is particularly relevant to foster the creation of new and sustainable training opportunities, organized by RMs operating at the local/ national level, that can adopt and/or adapt the several training schemes and courses already ongoing in Europe.

This preliminary report (D2.1) will focus primarily on the development of Task 2.1, titled "Assessing the current training, networking, mobility, and funding per segment of the RM community & creating an open smart database," showcasing the work developed by NOVA (leaders of WP2) in collaboration with the WP2 partners ASTP, EARMA, CHX, JANSSEN, and UNAE, and with the input of all the other RM Roadmap partner institutions. As a preliminary report, it will focus on the information collected by desk research, complemented by data provided directly from institutions responsible for training, networking, mobility, and funding opportunities as part of our data collection task in the RM Roadmap project.

2. Background

2.1 Research Managers (RMs) within the R&I Ecosystem

Research and Innovation (R&I) ecosystem has been rapidly growing over the past few decades, with a multiplicity of opportunities for research funding, transnational cooperation, networking, and mobility, leading to a flourishing and increasingly competitive environment. This led to an increasing demand for human resources for science, technology, and innovation management activities, for communication and dissemination of science, and for science policy and assessment of the scientific, technological, and higher education systems. R&I needs not only excellent researchers but also highly skilled professionals working in research administration, research management, knowledge transfer and exploitation, science communication, research governance, and research policy to release the full potential of R&I at institutional, national, and international levels (Oliveira *et al.*, 2022, p.6). Even though these professionals do not perform direct research tasks, they partner with researchers in common working ecosystems. **These professionals are the Research Managers (RMs).**

Research Managers can operate *upstream of research* – to attract/advocate for/define a strategy for research funding, projects, and partnerships (with academia, industry, and many other sectors like the social, educational, culture, etc.); during the research – to *support the research activity itself* (e.g. post-award management, technological platform management, ethical compliance management, intellectual property management); and downstream of research – *broadening the impact of research* (e.g. outreach, science communication, facilitating the impact on understanding, learning & participation; creativity, culture, and society; social welfare; commerce & economy; public policy, law & services; health, wellbeing & animal welfare; production; the environment; practitioners & professional services (Agostinho, *et al.*, 2018). RMs also develop their work in cross-cutting issues that are transversal to upstream and downstream phases of research, such as responsible research and innovation, gender, diversity and inclusion, ethics, and several broader areas of research development.

Figure 1 - Level of action where RMs operate (Oliveira *et. al.*, 2022)

For R&I to reach its full potential at the institutional, national, and international levels, the Council of the European Union (2021), in its latest document updated in November 2021, highlighted a priority area for the future governance of the European Research Area (ERA): Amplifying access to research and innovation excellence across the Union (2021). Considering this, the Council acknowledged the need to strengthen the strategic capabilities of Europe's performing public research organizations and launched ERA Action 17 (2022) for the period of 2022-2024. ERA Action 17 aims to improve the European R&I system across the entire ERA through a Research Management Initiative that expects to involve at least 100 public research-performing/funding organizations by the end of 2024. This acknowledgment and focus on encouraging cooperation across institutions in the field of science management.

ERA Action 17 works by organizing workshops with stakeholder groups, Member States and Associate Countries' representatives to collect expectations/recommendations. One challenge to be addressed relates to the need for upskilling, to improve the skills and competencies of Research Managers, to inform about existing training and mobility opportunities, and to ensure the quality in training and mobility provided.

2.2 Research Managers: main skills and competencies

In the last few decades, the responsibilities of research managers have expanded significantly to include a variety of interrelated tasks (Agostinho, *et al.*, 2018) and are now expected to manoeuvre through the challenging environment while juggling several factors and adjusting for shifting conditions. Successful professionals must have a multi-talented and mission-oriented personality (Shambrook & Roberts, 2011). RMs must also have a wide range of skills and knowledge to support high-quality research (Green and Langley, 2009).

Tauginiene (2009) distinguishes three main skills and competencies that RMs must have: 1) **to generate, interpret and distribute information**: to recognize the latest information, understand and communicate information at all stages of the development and management of grants; 2) **to communicate at many levels**: between researchers, researchers and RMs, between RMs and other stakeholders; 3) **to solve problems with high integrity, and ethics**. Moreover, the emergence of new challenges and opportunities means that RMs must adapt to continuous change and, therefore, integrate competencies to reflect these changes.

Empirical studies can also provide insightful information about the most relevant RM skills and competencies. An online survey conducted at the beginning of 2016 (Davis-Hamilton & Marina 2018) of RESADM-L subscribers revealed that RMs need important attributes: **rules and regulations knowledge, customer service and collaboration, attention to details, problem-solving skills, pressure and multitasking skills, communication, and organizational skills, as well as continuous learning**.

A study developed by HÉTFA (Virágh *et al.*, 2020) was conducted through an online survey (136 responses from 31 different European countries), online semi-structured interviews (selected 9 RM that fill in the survey from different European countries), and a workshop (organized by HÉTFA Research Institute with the involvement of Hungarian stakeholders, including researchers, RMs and representatives of research funding organizations to present and validate the results of the survey) on the subject. Looking at their main conclusions, we can see that, as regards competencies, the perceived most important ones are **reliability, efficiency, flexibility, planning and strategic thinking, team building, and motivation building**.

The relevance of transferable skills and competencies for RMs is also highlighted in other studies. In the last edition of the Research Administration as a Professional (RAAAP) global survey (Kerridge *et al.*, 2023), and looking at the results from the European respondents, we can see that five transferable skills were considered relevant for getting into the RM profession: **organisational skills** (74.0%),

motivation to learn new things (65.9%), **communication skills** (65.3%), **team player / personable** (60.9%) and **multitasking skills** (59.8%). When looking at the entry to the RM profession, it is also worth noticing that, in the top 3 challenges in the initial role of a Research Manager, the respondents selected **Lack of Knowledge** (54.5%), **Lack of training** (38.3%) and **Lack of career frameworks** (36.1%).

More recently, the CARDEA project produced a survey and a report analysing the competence profile of RM. In the analysis presented, the results indicate that research managers **recognize the need for further training in the areas of competence they perceive as essential**. This will enable them to increase effectiveness, particularly in soft skills such as **attention to detail, critical thinking, decision-making, relationship management skills, and developing and managing partnerships with internal and external stakeholders** (O'Regan & Saporito, 2023, pp.42-46).

WP1 will identify the main skills and competencies needed for Research Managers, while WP2 will cross-reference them with the professional development activities available. For a comprehensive literature review on skills and competencies see WP1 deliverable D1.1 Preliminary report on ERA-wide landscape.

2.3 The role of RM professional associations in providing opportunities for professional development

Given that research management professionals require a multitude of transferable skills and diverse technical knowledge, the existence of training programs, mobility options, and networking opportunities for RM is essential. Professional associations, either formal or informal, play an important role in providing and fostering these opportunities for professional development.

Networking, mobility, and training opportunities supported by professional associations enhance career growth and provide RMs with a holistic view of their profession (Kerridge, 2012, pp-50-52). The **ability to network** with people in the same professional area and **exchange knowledge, ideas, and best practices** is one of the main advantages. Finding people who have had similar difficulties through networking promotes continuous debates to **create professional standards** and **spread knowledge**. RM Professional associations usually provide venues for **in-person meetings, online discussion boards, and communication channels** that enable the sharing of information, helping the profession's general growth and advancement through a variety of channels. RM Professional associations place a high priority on training, and as part of their missions, several formal and informal RM associations organize **training sessions** and, some of them, **certification programmes**. These initiatives aim to develop professional norms and practices while giving participants the chance to advance their expertise in their specialized sectors. Furthermore, professional associations contribute to ongoing

RM Roadmap_NOVA_WP2_D2.1_Preliminary report on professional development

education and research about the profession through various publications, including journals, magazines, white papers, webinars, and blogs.

With the aim to foster a wider recognition of the RM profession and a clear career pathway for professional development, several RM professional associations developed **Professional Development Frameworks** that define professional standards for RM that highlight the main roles and competencies expected from RM at various stages of their career. Some examples are:

- The Association of Research Managers and Administrators (ARMA) developed the **ARMA Professional Development Framework (PDF)** and other acronyms with 21 areas that include developing proposals, managing project finance, knowledge exchange and business development, and supporting postgraduate researchers. The roles are divided into seven broad categories: drafting proposals, project life, translation, postgraduate researchers, policy and governance, management information and related functions, and service organization and delivery. Each role is also described from three different perspectives related to the level of responsibility – operation, management, and leadership.
- BESTPRAC created the **Research Support Staff (RSS) Framework** (BESTPRAC – COST TN 1302, n.d.) which identifies the various roles, tasks, and skills performed by an RM in the frame of the project lifecycle. It considers four stages i) before the proposal; ii) proposal; iii) grant preparation and, iv) project. In this professional framework, three other perspectives are proposed: Research Administrator, Funding Advisor / Liaison Manager, and Project Manager.
- The **ARMS Professional Development Framework (PDF)** (ARMS, n.d.) identifies the knowledge base needed to become an effective research management expert in the Australian region and maps the ARMS range of programs available or needed to provide this knowledge. The PDF lists six basic areas of knowledge and three levels of knowledge enhancement – foundations, management, and leadership. Moving from one level of knowledge to another usually requires familiarity with the previous level of knowledge.
- Southern African Research and Innovation Management Association (SARIMA) created the **SARIMA Professional Competency Framework (PCF)** outlining nine key skills for research managers covering research development, funding, ethics, and integrity (SARIMA, n.d.), under 3 levels of responsibility: Level 1 - Administrative/Operational, Level 2 – Management, and Level 3 – Leadership/Strategic. SARIMA, through its International Professional Recognition Council (IPRC), promotes professional recognition as one option for the professionalisation of research managers in Southern Africa. By submitting a portfolio of evidence, candidates can have their prior learning and experience, as well as their current competencies, reviewed by their peers on the IPRC. The submission of portfolios is voluntary, and candidates can apply for recognition in one of two designations: Research Management Professional (RMP) and

RM Roadmap_NOVA_WP2_D2.1_Preliminary report on professional development

Senior Research Management Professional (SRMP).

- It should also be stressed that the CARDEA project - Enabling professionalization of research management has developed the CARDEA Matrix Framework as a base for a future career framework for Research Managers within the European Research Area (ERA) that can be simple and interoperable, such as defining levels (RM 1 to RM4).

These professional career frameworks are important for RMs to understand their professional roles and responsibilities, and plan their professional and career development, and target the training, mobility, and networking activities necessary to achieve their career goals.

In conclusion, by offering networking, mobility, and training opportunities that advance RMs' knowledge, skills, and competencies, professional groups play a critical role in their professional growth. Their activities provide RMs the chance to network with colleagues, share expertise, and set high expectations for themselves. Additionally, several of them developed professional development frameworks that specify the required capabilities and responsibilities of RMs at various career phases, such as the ARMA, BESTPRAC, ARMS, and SARIMA frameworks, promoting the standardization of the profession and enabling employers and RMs to successfully organize their careers, pinpoint opportunities for development, and partake in pertinent activities.

WP1 will develop an European Professional Development Framework for Research Managers, while WP2 will cross-reference the RM professional areas with the professional development activities available. For a comprehensive literature review on Professional Development Frameworks see WP1 deliverable D1.1 Preliminary report on ERA-wide landscape.

2.4 RM Roadmap contribution to RMs professional development

In the last decades, and with the enhancement of the RM profession across Europe, opportunities for RM professional growth are expanding. This includes the creation of formal and informal associations and networks, at the European and national level, but also the establishment of a diverse set of training, networking and mobility opportunities promoted by these associations and by other institutions, public and private, from the educational and professional sector. Up to now, these professional development activities are scattered in multiple institutions and sources, and thus not easily available for RMs that are entering into the profession or RMs working in countries or institutions where these opportunities are still lacking. Mapping and showcasing of training, mobility, networking, and funding opportunities for research managers across Europe in an open online tool is crucial for several reasons:

RM Roadmap_NOVA_WP2_D2.1_Preliminary report on professional development

- First, there are continually new skills, competences, and best practices being developed in the field of RM. We can keep up with the most recent advancements and make sure that RMs have access to pertinent and current training options by undertaking a thorough mapping exercise. As a result, they may broaden RM knowledge, pick up new skills, and maintain their competitiveness in their jobs.
- Second, networking and mobility are essential to professional advancement. Exposure to a range of viewpoints, possibilities for experience, and collaborative opportunities are extremely beneficial for research managers. Moreover, these opportunities are important because of the profession's strong on-the-job learning character due to the ever-changing requirements and lack of specific formal training. We can find platforms, events, and projects that promote knowledge sharing, peer learning, and the development of meaningful professional relationships by mapping networking and mobility possibilities. These possibilities can encourage creativity, encourage interdisciplinary cooperation, and provide research managers access to new career options.
- Third, funding is a critical aspect of research management. Identifying funding opportunities specific to research managers ensures that they have access to resources and necessary support for their professional growth. This includes grants, scholarships, and other funding mechanisms that can facilitate participation in training programs, conferences, and professional development activities.
- Furthermore, mapping these different available opportunities across Europe will enable the identification of geographical areas and RM segment areas that are missing opportunities for professional development.
- Also, bringing together one single online tool with opportunities for professional development across Europe will promote wider accessibility, also including regions where RM is less developed. Comparing the results from this mapping exercise with the data that will be collected via the RM Roadmap survey, which will ask the RM community about their level of participation in these opportunities and opinions about the missing ones, will support recommendations in that regard.

3. Methodology

In order to understand the professional development opportunities for RM in Europe, WP2 combined desk research with the development of an online template to collect specific data on training, networking, mobility, and funding opportunities currently available across Europe. We have also collected data on RM networks, as these will be helpful to map further training, networking, mobility, and funding opportunities. As such, the following steps were undertaken:

1. **Development of desk research**, considering the main studies, reports, and papers already available on the related topic, in order to:
2. Understand the main skills and competencies of Research Managers;
 - Collect already available data on RM training needs and opportunities.

Creation of an online template (see Annex 2) to collect training, networking, and mobility data, as well as funding opportunities. For that, it was important to stocktake current online tools disseminating training, networking, mobility, and/or funding opportunities in order to select the main data entries and types of information to be mapped and, later on, included in the online tool.

3. **Definition of the scope of the mapping of the training, mobility, networking and funding opportunities for Research Managers:**
 - **Definition of Research Managers:** for this mapping, and taking into account the framework of the aforementioned project, the definition of Research Managers (RM) in the current mapping covers the different areas of specialization of these professionals working in both Research Performing Organizations, Research Funding Organizations, and other (private companies, NGOs), including tasks as (but not limited to):
 - pre-award
 - post-award
 - innovation
 - science communication
 - outreach/community
 - impact
 - ethics

RM Roadmap_NOVA_WP2_D2.1_Preliminary report on professional development

- policy
 - infrastructure
 - data management
 - research assessment
 - researcher development/ talent development
 - lab management
- **Type of opportunities for professional development:** The following categories were defined:

(1) Training activities	Training courses, modules, degrees, programmes, etc.
(2) Mobility opportunities	Learning or professional mobility programmes for peer learning, job shadowing, internships, etc.
(3) Networking activities	Activities may include training and mobility, but the main aim is to provide networking opportunities for the participants. For example, Annual meetings of the RM associations, conferences targeted to RM-related topics, thematic groups, etc.
(4) Funding schemes	Funding programmes or opportunities that support RM professional development, such as mobility programmes, support to participate in events (such as conferences) or in training, open applications for projects targeted to RM topics, etc.
(5) Research Managers Networks	Formal and informal associations, platforms, and communities of practice. For thematic groups that are part of an association, please include it in "networking opportunities".

RM Roadmap_NOVA_WP2_D2.1_Preliminary report on professional development

- **Inclusion criteria:** The following criteria were considered for inclusion,
 - Targeted to research managers (RM);
 - Frequent opportunities (in opposition to isolated actions that may not be available in the future);
 - Open for participation (in opposition to opportunities only open to RM from a particular institution).

 - **Exclusion criteria:** The following criteria were considered for exclusion,
 - Info sessions about specific funding calls/programmes;
 - Non-regular training sessions;
 - Institutional internal training not available for external participants.
4. **Validating the data protection procedures** to put in place regarding data collection (in alignment with the project's data management plan).

 5. **Mapping the institutions responsible for providing training, networking, mobility and funding opportunities**, at the EU and national levels.
 - Collecting their main contacts and responsible persons for this area.

 6. **Inviting all institutions to fill in the online template** with the requested information on these activities.

 7. **Control and validate the data furnished by the institutions.**

4. Preliminary Results

The preliminary results function as a simulation exercise to test the methodology and help identify gaps in the methodology, that will be further developed once a more robust sample is collected. They are described in an extended summary in Annex 3, organized in a table with the following areas: Geographical Coverage (International, European, or National), Country and Opportunity Typology (Training, Mobility, Networking, Funding, and Research Manager Networks).

A total of 213 professional development opportunities targeting RM were collected in our preliminary mapping exercise. As far as the typology of opportunity (Figure 2), 46.48% are related to RM Networks (n=99), 31.46% are Training activities (n= 67), 11.74% are Networking activities (n=25), 7.98% are related to the Funding schemes (n=17), and 2.35% are related to the Mobility activities (n=5).

Figure 2 - Type of professional development opportunities for RMs

Regarding geographic coverage, we categorize each opportunity as “International, European, or National”, depending on the region of the world the offer applies to (and not from where it is originated). As such, “National” indicates that the opportunity is available in one EU country, “European” to more than one country in the EU and “International” if the opportunity is offered beyond Europe. Most of the professional development opportunities mapped are National (n=151, 70.89%), followed by opportunities at the “European” level (n=44, 20.66%) and at the International level (n=18, 8.45%) Regarding the National category we were able to identify professional opportunities in the following countries, according to the higher number of activities collected:

RM Roadmap_NOVA_WP2_D2.1_Preliminary report on professional development

Portugal, Germany, United Kingdom, Spain, Italy, Switzerland, France, Norway, Poland, Belgium, Denmark, Finland, The Netherlands, Turkey, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Hungary, Iceland Republic of Ireland and Northern Ireland, Albania, Austria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Greece, Lithuania, Romania, Scotland, Serbia, Slovak Republic, Slovenia, Sweden, Ukraine.

Figure 3 - National Coverage of the professional activities for RMs across Europe

It is important to note that these are preliminary data collected by NOVA over the last 6 months of the project. As such, there is still a bias related to the opportunities in countries where NOVA and the RM Roadmap partners have a greater engagement. To overcome this limitation, from September 2023 onwards, and as the RM Roadmap Ambassadors begin to engage in the project activities, they will be invited to collaborate by identifying other opportunities not included before, as well as engaging with their national community to support a higher engagement/ number of responses from their country (addressing institutions already contacted but that did not submit information on the online template). Since the collection of data will continue throughout the project, with its milestone in August 2024 with the presentation of the online tool, we are confident that we will be able to achieve a more complete and inclusive mapping exercise.

4.1 Training Opportunities

Training activities represent a total of 31.46% (n=67) of the professional development opportunities. From the 67 training activities mapped, 67.16% (n=45) are **National training across 12 different**

countries, 25.37% (n=17) are training at the European level, and 7.46% (n=5) are training at the International level.

Training opportunities for Research Managers have not always been readily available and it is interesting to note that **59.70% (n= 40) of the training activities mapped started in the last 3 years.**

Figure 4 - Availability of the Training Opportunities

From these relatively new training activities, 57.30% (n=23) are provided at the national level, 25.00% at European level (n=10) and 17.5% (n=7) at the International level. This may reveal that the awareness of the need to provide specific training for RMs has more recently reached the national stakeholders. On the opposite side, one third of the **training activities that exist for a longer period of time** (more than 5 and 10 years) are provided at the **European and International level** (33.33%, n= 9).

The target audience for the training appears to come from a variety of educational backgrounds, ranging from undergraduate students to Ph.D. holders, but with a strong **focus on continued professional development**. If you characterize the training regarding the “Level of study of target audience”, we can say that 94.03% (n=63) of the **training activities targeted RM professionals aiming for “continuing professional training”**, while only 5.97% (n= 4) define students (undergraduate student, postgraduate student, master student, Ph.D. student, Ph.D. holder) as the main target audience.

Regarding the different levels of professional experience of the target audience, more than one third

RM Roadmap_NOVA_WP2_D2.1_Preliminary report on professional development

of the training activities (34.33%, n=23) are **open to all levels of experience**. **Training targeting RMs in the beginning of their career are predominant**, representing 86.57% (n=58), divided in 17.91% (n=12) of training not requiring any RM experience, 29.85% (n=20) for RMs with 1-2 years' experience and 38.81% (n=26) for RMs with 2-5 years' experience.

About the total duration of the training opportunities, 65.37% (n=44) of the training activities have a **short duration** (less than 1 week), followed by long-duration training (more than 6 months) with 13.43% (n=12) and Medium duration training (from 1 week to 6 months) with 17.91% (n=12). Only 2 training activities were indicated to be self-paced/ self-study.

Figure 5 - Duration of the Training Opportunities

The topics covered by the training activities are varied: Pre-award, Post-award, Science Communication, Ethics, Gender Equality and Diversity, Infrastructure, Data Management, Impact, Policy, Innovation, as well as transferable skills and topics such as leadership and development of RM services and offices. It is worth noting that 57.73% (n=36) of the **training activities focused on more than three topics** (as the ones mentioned before).

Figure 6 – Topics of the mapped RM training activities

The availability of training resources varies depending on the specific training, but for 59.70% (n=40) the **training materials are available for the participants**. It is worth noting that only 2 training activities mentioned that their resources are open access to all interested. Still 29.85% (n=20) of the training opportunities do not have their resources available online.

There are several possibilities for certification or accreditation for the training opportunities specified in the online template such as certificates of participation (35.82%, n= 24), professional certificates (22.38%, n=15) or credits that help students advance academically (11.94%, n= 8) or micro-credentials (1.49%, n=1). However, **a considered amount of training opportunities (28.36% (n=19) does not offer any kind of accreditation**.

4.2 Mobility and Networking Opportunities

The preliminary data include only 5 **Mobility opportunities**, representing a total of 2.35% (n=5) of the mapped professional development opportunities divided in 60.00% (n=3) national mobilities and 40.00% (n= 2) mobilities within Europe. Mobilities' targeted to RMs were also categorized either as Institutional mobility schemes, provided by research performing institutions, universities or other institutions from the Research and Innovation ecosystem, or as RM Associations mobility schemes,

RM Roadmap_NOVA_WP2_D2.1_Preliminary report on professional development

provided by RM informal or formal professional associations (see Annex 3). All mobility schemes aimed to provide opportunities for RMs to continue their professional development and are open to RMs with all levels of experience.

Most of the mobility schemes are already available for some time to the RM community, with 60.00% (n=3) for more than 5 years and 20.00% (n=1) for more than 10 years. One of the mobility schemes is being organised for the first time (20.00%, n=1).

The information about “the skills developed by participating in the mobility of our online template” (question 2.6.3 in Annex 2) allowed us to understand that mobilities give the participants the chance to grow and improve a variety of research management-related abilities. By gaining new information, resources, and views, the participants increase their research management abilities. It should be also highlighted that it promotes the growth of professional networks by enabling encounters with managers of science and research from other nations, and this kind of interaction opens the door to upcoming partnerships and collaborations. Finally, it was also pointed out in question 2.6.3 “Indicate the skills developed by participating in the mobility of our online template” (Annex 2) that they improve comprehension of the policies, programs, and activities of the European Research Area. Thanks to this understanding, the participants can successfully negotiate the complicated terrain of European research. This means that mobility improves participants’ ability, skills and self-assurance needed to collaborate successfully in global teams and projects while navigating cultural barriers. Additionally, peer-to-peer experiences, knowledge, and successful case studies help them become aware of best practices in scientific and research administration.

In terms of **Networking**, we have 25 of the entries in the template, representing 11.74% of the mapped professional development opportunities. The **large majority (88.00%, n=22) of the networking opportunities occur at the national level**, while only 2 international networking opportunities were included in this preliminary mapping exercise. According to the data collected, **participation is free for 60.00%** (n=15) of the collected Networking activities, while the remaining 40.00% require a fee to participate. The same proportion of free/paid networking activities is observed for activities organized at national or international levels.

A more in-depth examination of Networking activities identified that many fall within the framework of Working groups under funded projects; Annual meetings/conferences of professional associations, RM Days, Retreats, and Regular RM gatherings. The main areas covered by the networking activity were identified as Post-award; Innovation; Impact; Policy; Knowledge transfer; Pre-award; Ethics; Infrastructure; Data management; Research assessment; Researcher development/ talent development; Leading a team/ office; Science communication; Outreach/community; Lab

management; Raising awareness of RM; News on EU research funding and policy; Gender (e.g. gender equality/equity, diversity, and inclusion, GEP development, and implementation); Public engagement; Open science / open access; Legal / Finance.

Figure 7 - Cost of Networking activities

Regarding the format of the networking activity, the collected information suggests that there is **diversity in the format of networking activities for Research Managers**: 32% are blended; 48% in-person, and 20% online. It is crucial to highlight that the varied formats offer participants a variety of possibilities to make contacts and relationships within the research management community.

About the format of the networking activity, it is important to mention that the networking activity includes a variety of events and activities intended at encouraging cooperation, information exchange, and professional growth among different types of professionals. Annual conferences such as KoWi Annual Conference (Germany), Journeys from Foundation for National Scientific Computing (Portugal), seminars from Irish Knowledge Transfer Association Annual Conference (Ireland), meetings like Monday Morning from the Swiss RM community (Switzerland) and working groups like ARMA's Special Interest Groups (or 'SIGs') (UK) are examples of events that bring together professionals such as research managers, data managers, administrators, and policymakers. These events might be described as places for debate, ideas exchange, and the sharing of best practices in areas such as: research data management, open science, technology transfer, and EU research and innovation financing. These meetings frequently include networking opportunities as well as talks on current subjects, challenges, and opportunities confronting the community.

4.3 RM associations and communities of practice across Europe

Formal or informal RM professional associations play an important role in providing and promoting opportunities for professional development to research managers, as they often organize meetings, online discussions, training sessions, and some, certification programmes. These initiatives aim to develop professional standards and practices and provide participants with the opportunity to increase their professional knowledge in their field of expertise.

A total of 99 **RM Networks** were mapped in our preliminary mapping exercise. These RM networks include formal and informal associations and networks, considering a broad understanding of RM of the RM profession, including science communication, research ethics, research infrastructures, and data, to name a few specific areas. To avoid potential repetitions and errors in the entries, a more thorough screening of the raw data will be conducted at a second stage.

A detailed list of RM Networks can be found in Annex 3, organized by International Networks (9.09%, n=9), European Networks (10.10%, n=10), and National Networks (80.81%, n=80) **existing in 27 different countries across Europe.**

4.4 Funding Opportunities

In relation to the **Funding opportunities**, we could identify 17 funding schemes that can support RM activities, mostly European funding opportunities (88.24%, n=15), one International (5.88%), and one National (5.88%), particularly in Albania. Regarding the characterization of these opportunities, it can be said that 88.24% are characterized as Institutional grants, meaning that they consist of applications by representatives of institutions to get funding for mobility programmes that individuals can benefit from later on if the funding is approved, and 11.76% are Individual travel grants, in which the direct beneficiaries are individuals.

It should also be highlighted that the funding options span a wide variety of subjects, including program-level collaboration with national R&D policymakers, assistance for research infrastructure, excellence programs, dissemination and exploitation of findings, and others. Moreover, the funding opportunities focus on topics such as value generation, European citizen science campaigns, and research ethics.

5. Challenges Encountered

While we have achieved considerable progress, it is crucial to highlight that this is ongoing work because data collection will continue until 2024. Our method of gathering data is long-term, which is one of its benefits because it will allow us to have a comprehensive picture of the phenomena we are researching, and it enables to assess necessary changes over a long period of time. The dataset given in this report is a snapshot of the information available as of 16.06.2023.

Data will be subject to future modifications, updates, and adjustments (such as cleaning up any repeated entries in the online template). As we continue to collect data, our understanding of the issue will likely grow, and new insights may emerge.

Despite these drawbacks, the information gathered thus far offers insightful information. The analysis performed serves as the basis for our continued study and will provide a good basis to support future recommendations on training, mobility, networking, and funding available for RM across Europe. We anticipate being able to give a more thorough and accurate analysis in the following reports as we move forward and gather additional data. Regarding the global risks of WP2 tasks and potential mitigation measures please also see Annex 1 - Concept Note.

6. Conclusions

In summary, this preliminary report on professional development opportunities (D2.1) provides a comprehensive overview of the existing range of options available to research managers (RMs) in terms of training opportunities, networking, RM-networks, funding, and mobility within the scope of the RM Roadmap initiative. Through extensive desk research and data collection from an online template, invaluable insights were obtained, illuminating the current state-of-the-art of these opportunities. In addition, the study highlights the objectives and need for developing a one-stop-shop online tool to enhance accessibility to relevant information for RM professional development across Europe and evaluating the available options against the recognized needs of the RM community.

Based on our analysis, we would like to emphasize several key aspects:

- The rising significance of Research Managers (RMs) in the Research and Innovation (R&I) ecosystem and their function in research activities are introduced in the report. It highlights the diversity of abilities and talents necessary for RMs, like communication, problem-solving,

RM Roadmap_NOVA_WP2_D2.1_Preliminary report on professional development

information management, and flexibility, demanding a constant upskilling of RM professionals. The report also emphasizes the significance of professional associations in providing networking, mobility, RM-networks, and training opportunities for RMs.

- Given the preliminary nature of the results shown, it is too early to advance general conclusions. One interesting aspect to highlight, however, is the observation that most of the training offers for RM listed were created in the last 3 years. This shows that there is high demand for training in RMs and that this is a dynamic field where substantial progress may happen in the next few years. Another interesting finding is the existence of close to 100 RM networks and associations across Europe. This may suggest that there is already a certain level of organization and representativity of RM communities, although with some level of invisibility. It will be interesting to analyse if there are specificities at geographical coverage and/or RM thematic area.
- Other points of analysis will be considered and may focus on: opportunities available for the different levels of professional experience and seniority; specialisation levels of the training according to the geographical coverage and/or RM thematic area (segment); the costs and access of participation, etc.
- Examples of professional development and competencies frameworks were given, designed by organizations like ARMA, BESTPRAC, ARMS, and SARIMA that outline the responsibilities and skills required of RMs at various career phases. While the information collected and described in this report starts to unveil an overview of the training and mobility patterns of RMs across Europe, it will be important to understand to what extent the available competence frameworks relate to the existing training and mobility opportunities, and whether they can be used to identify gaps to improve the current offer.
- While the primary focus of this preliminary report does not entail conducting a comprehensive analysis of the impact or effectiveness of the professional development opportunities, it is important to note that the report does not burrow into the satisfaction levels of participants, or the outcomes achieved through these opportunities.
- The preliminary findings do not address ethical issues related to the chances for research managers to advance their careers. Further on in our timeline, in the training, networking, mobility, and funding procedures, it will be crucial to take conclusions about possible ethical issues relating to accessibility, justice, inclusiveness, and data protection. As a recommendation that may be suggested in the final data gathered, it is also important to

RM Roadmap_NOVA_WP2_D2.1_ Preliminary report on professional development

make sure that everyone has an equal opportunity to participate, protecting private information, maintaining transparency in the selection processes, and addressing potential conflicts of interest within RM associations and funding opportunities.

As a concluding remark, it is crucial to keep in mind that this report's major goal is to map existing training, networking, mobility, and funding opportunities for Research Management (RM) rather than develop innovative training programs. This preliminary report basically acts as a starting point for deeper research, recommendations, and the incorporation of findings into the overall roadmap for the Research Manager (RM) System in Europe. This means that this preliminary study opens the door for a thorough comprehension of the potential already existing and creates the framework for further cooperation and advancement in upgrading the professional development environment for research managers.

7. References

Agostinho, M., Alves, C. M., Aresta, S., Borrego, F., Borlido-Santos, J., Cortez, J., Costa, T. L., Lopes, J. A., Moreira, S., Santos, J., Trindade, M., Varela, C. & Vidal, S.. (2018). The interface of science: the case for a broader definition of research management. *Perspectives: Policy and Practice in Higher Education*, 24(1), 19-27. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603108.2018.1543215>

Australasian Research Management Society (ARMS). (n.d.). ARMS Education, Training and Professional Development Opportunities. Retrieved June 20, 2023, from <https://www.researchmanagement.org.au/professional-development>

BESTPRAC - COST TN 1302. (n.d.). Engaging in the European Research Area. Retrieved June 6, 2023, from https://www.bestprac.eu/fileadmin/mediapool-bestprac/documents/WS-Brussels/BESTPRAC_Inlet.pdf

Council of the European Union. (2021). Interinstitutional File:2021/0230 (NLE) | COUNCIL RECOMMENDATION on a Pact for Research and Innovation in Europe. Retrieved June 2, 2023, from <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-13701-2021-INIT/en/pdf>

Davis-Hamilton, Z., & Marina, S. (2018). What Makes a Research Administrator? | Pulse. Society of Research Administrators International (SRAI). Retrieved June 19, 2023, from <https://www.srainternational.org/blogs/martha-jack/2018/04/27/what-makes-a-research-administrator-pulse>

European Commission (2021). European Research Area Policy Agenda - Overview of actions for the period 2022-2024. Retrieved July 17, 2023, from https://commission.europa.eu/system/files/2021-11/ec_rtd_era-policy-agenda-2021.pdf doi:10.2777/52110

RM Roadmap_NOVA_WP2_D2.1_Preliminary report on professional development

European Commission (2022). Era Policy Agenda – Action 17 – April 2022- working document. Retrieved July 17, 2023, from [https://era.gv.at/public/documents/4606/17 -
_Enhance_public_research_institutions_strategic_capacity_explanatory_docum_4Fflm4c.pdf](https://era.gv.at/public/documents/4606/17_-_Enhance_public_research_institutions_strategic_capacity_explanatory_docum_4Fflm4c.pdf)

Green, J., & Langley, D. (2009). Professionalising Research Management. Research Global. Retrieved June 19, 2023, from <https://snowballmetrics.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/2009-professionalising-research-management.pdf>

Kerridge, S. R. (2012). Electronic research administration: Reflections on Research Management and Administration (RMA) in UK universities and in particular on Electronic Research Administration (ERA) and its perceived effect on the quality and quantity of research. University of Sunderland. Retrieved June 15, 2023, from https://sure.sunderland.ac.uk/id/eprint/3290/1/Electronic_Research_Administration_-_Report.pdf

Kerridge, S., Fischer, M., Oliveira, C. I., & Dutta, M. (2023). RAAAP-3: HIBARMA - How I Became a Research Manager and Administrator [Collection]. figshare. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.c.6139509>

Oliveira, C., Trindade, M., Varela, C., Campelo, D., Domingues, A. and Martins, M. (2022). foRMAtion International Curriculum for Future Research Managers and Administrators. Curriculum developed within the project 'Innovative and smart module for potential Research Managers and Administrators in higher education – foRMAtion'. <https://doi.org/10.34619/9bxi-h4cg>

O'Regan, M. K., & Saporito, P. (n.d.). CARDEA Survey Summary of Results. Retrieved June 15, 2023, from https://www.ucc.ie/en/media/research/cardea/Cardea_Report_Summary_FINAL_Discl.pdf

SARIMA. (n.d.). Annexure A Professional Competency Framework (PCF). Retrieved June 20, 2023, from https://www.sarima.co.za/wp-content/uploads/2019/02/pc_framework.pdf

Shambrook, J., & Roberts, T. J. (2011). 2010 Profile of a Research Administrator. Research Management Review, 18(1). Retrieved June 19, 2023, from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ980454.pdf>

Tauginienė, L. (2009). The roles of a research administrator at a university. Public Policy and Administration, 1, 45-56.

Virágh, E., Zsár, V., & Balázs, Z. (2020). Research Management and Administration: The Relevance of Specific Education and Training Programmes. Budapest: Research Institute and Center for Economic and Social Analysis (HÉTFA). Retrieved June 9, 2023, from https://hetfa.hu/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/22_tanulm%C3%A1ny_v4.pdf

RM ROADMAP

 rmroadmap.eu

 [@rmroadmap](https://twitter.com/rmroadmap)

 linkedin.com/company/rmroadmap

RM-ROADMAP project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement number 101058475.

WORK PACKAGE 2 - TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT

MAIN GOALS:

- ▶ Creating an online tool to increase the accessibility for the RM community of information on existing funding and training;
- ▶ Recommending training that could create synergies with a future Europe-wide training and networking scheme;
- ▶ Fostering the creation of communities of practice among trainers to exchange best practices and to promote the internationalisation of existing training.

MAIN TASKS, DURATION AND PARTNERS INVOLVED:

TASKS	DURATION	PARTNERS INVOLVED
Task 2.1 - Assessing the current training, networking and funding per segment of the RM community & creating an open smart database	M1-M30 [Sept 2022 – Feb 2025]	Leader NOVA Partners ASTP, EARMA, CHX, JANSSEN, UNAE
Task 2.2 - Producing survey, gap analysis and recommendations to fulfil the identified training and networking needs	M1-M24 [Sept 2022 – Aug 2024]	Leader NOVA Partners HETFA, ASTP UNAE
Task 2.3 - Fostering the creation of communities of practice among trainers	M6-M36 [Feb 2023 – Aug 2025]	Leader NOVA Partners ALL
Task 2.4 - Fostering national and thematic communities (in Widening Countries) including research infrastructure: RM community incubator.	M12-M36 [Aug 2023 – Aug 2025]	Leader: CYI Partners: NOVA, ASTP, UNAE

DELIVERABLES

- ▶ D 2.1 - Preliminary report on professional development opportunities (Aug 2023)
- ▶ D 2.2 - Online tool for professional development opportunities (Aug 2024)
- ▶ D 2.3 - Report on the professional development opportunities (Jun 2025)

		2022					2023					2024					2025																					
Task N°	Task Denomination	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	
		Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	
2.1	Assessing the current training, networking and funding per segment of the RM community & creating an open smart database																																					
	Stocktaking of current online tools																																					
	Identification of the main data entries																																					
	Creation of templates to collect: - training, mobility, networking and funding opportunities - training providers information																																					
	Definition of the scope of the mapping of the training, mobility, networking and funding opportunities																																					
	Validate the data protection procedures																																					
	Map the opportunities available and fill in templates (desk research and contacts)									Amb Meet																												
	Analysis of the preliminary results												D2.1																									
	Engagement with the ambassadors to identify opportunities available at institutional, local and national levels																			Amb Meet																		
	Contributing to the development of the online tool, to be undertaken by CARDEA																								D2.2													
	Finalization and promotion of the online tool																																					
	Engagement with the RM community to update present, discuss and finalize online tool/ report on the professional development opportunities																										Amb Meet											D2.3 Final Meet

Task 2.1 - Analysis of current training, networking and funding per segment of the RM community & creation of an open smart database

OBJECTIVES

- ▶ Review of current RM training, networking, mobility and funding, per segment of the community (per country and CoP);
- ▶ Create an online tool compiling the current offering and listing specific training opportunities per segment of the community (via the Crowdhelix recommender engine).

Connection to other RM Roadmap work packages and tasks

In the dissemination of the available training, networking, mobility and funding will need to consider/categorize them regarding the areas/ segments included in the RMA profession. This discussion will take place in WP1, namely in Task 1.2 Characterisation and Categorisation of the RM roles Currently Available in the ERA (HETFFA).

The main findings of the mapping will be disseminated online with an appropriate tool and platform. This task will be supported by EARMA and Crowdhelix in Task 4.6 Knowledge and Community Platform (KCP). As per the latter, the platform:

- Will provide an open-source database of non-confidential information gathered in WP1 and training materials from WP2.
- Will act as a DSS providing recommendations to users on relevant training and funding in their RM field of expertise.
- Will share information on available training, funding and RM strategies and promote greater levels of understanding of the various stakeholders in the Research and RM ecosystem.
- Will identify gaps in current RM offerings
- Will foster the debate about relevant topics by hosting a ‘forum for discussion’
- Will pool resources, talents and other capabilities of the diverse range of stakeholders, thereby strengthening the RM communities

Task 2.1 will require contacting and/or meeting the trainers and/or those responsible for training and networking opportunities. As such, it will contribute to mapping RM stakeholders in WP4 - Task 4.2 Dissemination.

This first contact with the trainers will be key to fostering the collaborations needed for the implementation of WP 2 Task 2.3 - Fostering the creation of communities of practice among trainers.

RM Roadmap partners involved

Leader: NOVA

Partners: HETFA, ASTP, EARMA, CHX, JANSSEN, UNA

Synergies with other actions and initiatives

- ▶ The Professional Development Frameworks of associations of RMAs, such as:
 - ARMA: <https://arma.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2018/08/PDF-Final.pdf>
 - SARIMA: https://www.sarima.co.za/wp-content/uploads/2019/02/pc_framework.pdf
 - BESTPRAC: http://www.bestprac-wiki.eu/Main_Page, etc.
- ▶ The results of the Research Administration as a Profession (RAAAP) survey, particularly regarding the training certificates and courses
- ▶ foRMAtion Intellectual Output 1 – mapping training offers
- ▶ V4+WB Network of Research Managers and Administrators (RMAs) – online expert pool and learning materials
- ▶ CARDEA work on mapping and disseminating training/ networking/ mobility/ funding opportunities
- ▶ EARMA Professional Development and Recognition Committee (PDRC)
- ▶ Other initiatives identified during the project

METHODOLOGY WITH CALENDARIZATION

ACTIVITY	START-END
<p>Stocktaking of current online tools disseminating training, networking, mobility and/ or funding opportunities</p>	October 2022
<p>Identification of the main data entries and types of information to be included in the online tool</p>	October - November 2022
<p>Creation of templates to collect training, networking and mobility data, as well as funding opportunities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Template per opportunity ● Template per training provider 	November 2022 early Dec. 2022 January 2023
<p>Definition of the scope of the mapping of the training, mobility, networking and funding opportunities:</p> <p>▶ Inclusion criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● All opportunities where RMAs are a target audience (event the ones where it is not limited to them – eg.: trainings for RMAs and researchers) ● Opportunities where RMAs can participate openly (meaning, not internal opportunities targeted only for RMAs from a particular institution) ● Opportunities at the international and national level, as such in English or in the national language ● No restriction to the type of training provider, including consultancies <p>▶ Exclusion criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Info sessions ● Non-regular training sessions/ ad-hoc opportunities ● Internal training not available for external participants 	Jan 2023
<p>Validate the data protection procedures to put in place regarding data collection (in articulation with the project’s data management plan)</p>	Jan - Feb 2023
<p>Desk research to map the opportunities available and fill in templates with preliminary information:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● RMA associations’ websites, documents and publications ● Papers and professional articles ● Past studies and results from previous surveys 	Jan 2023 – June 2023
<p>Validate and complete any information missing in the preliminary templates by contacting the contact points and trainers responsible for the mapped opportunities</p>	April 2023 – June 2023

METHODOLOGY WITH CALENDARIZATION

ACTIVITY	START-END
<p>Analysis of the preliminary results collected to compare the training/ networking & mobility/ funding and identify and discuss patterns, trends and gaps in terms of geographical (country and regional specifics), segments, opportunities formats, funding coverage, best practices, etc. Compilation of these results into <u>Deliverable 2.1 - Preliminary report on professional development opportunities</u></p>	<p>June 2023- August 2023</p>
<p>Engagement with the ambassadors to identify opportunities available at institutional, local and national levels:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Starting to engage in the 1st ambassadors' meeting ▶ Continuing with individual contacts (a repetition of task 5 to this target audience ▶ Using the Knowledge and Community Platform (KCP) 	<p>May 2023- May 2024</p>
<p>Contributing to the development of the online tool, to be undertaken by CARDEA, namely with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Co-definition of the main data entries ▶ Uploading/feeding the online tool with data previously collected with the training, networking & mobility and funding ▶ Collaborating in the organization of working groups/ focus groups to test the usability of the tool within the Roadmap Ambassadors' netwo ▶ Collaborating in the revision of the online tool, based on the recommendations collected in the usability tests/ activitie ▶ Collaborating in the promotion of the online tool 	<p>Sept. 2023 – Jun 2024</p>
<p>Finalization and promotion of the online tool <u>D 2.2 - Online tool for professional development opportunities</u></p>	<p>July- August 2024</p>
<p>Continuously updating and completing the database with new training, networking, mobility and funding opportunities. To do so, the following strategies will be undertaken:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Exploring with CARDEA the possibility for participants to submit information about the new opportunities directly in the online too ● Exploring with EARMA and Crowdhelix the possibilities of interaction in the 4.6 Knowledge and Community Platform (KCP). Namely, with an open forum or providing topics for discussion on the subject ● Actively disseminating the database in conferences and workshops targeted to the RM community 	<p>August 2024 - May 2025</p>

METHODOLOGY WITH CALENDARIZATION

ACTIVITY	START-END
Finalize the D2.3 - Report on the professional development opportunities (integrating the results from Task 2.2)	June 2025
Presentation & validation of the Report on the professional development opportunities - Brussels stakeholders dissemination meeting & Online dissemination conference by EARMA online	June 2025

Deliverables and outputs

- ▶ Templates to collect information on each training, networking, mobility, or funding opportunity
- D 2.1 - Preliminary report on professional development opportunities (Aug 2023)
- D 2.2 - Online tool for professional development opportunities (Aug 2024)
- D 2.3 - Report on the professional development opportunities (Jun 2025) – which will also integrate the results of Task 2.2

Target audience and stakeholders

- ▶ RM community in the ERA, in particular:
 - RM Roadmap ambassadors
 - Training providers in RM topics
- ▶ RMA associations, networks and informal communities of practice
- ▶ Universities, networks of universities & research institutions, university alliances, research institutions, companies, or any other institutions that employ RMs and/or that could promote institutional opportunities for their RM community
- ▶ Funding agencies
- ▶ Policymakers at national (Ministries) and international (ERA + EU Policy)

RISKS AND MITIGATION PLANS

RISK	RESIDUAL RISK LEVEL	MITIGATION MEASURE	RESPONSIBLE FOR MITIGATION MEASURES
<p>Exclusion of some professional roles within the RMA profession considering the broad definition of all the professionals at the interface of science</p>	<p>High level</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Close collaboration with the partner ASTP to provide information on RMAs in innovation ▶ Mapping of other associations or initiatives that represent or work closely with science communicators, brokers, data stewards, infrastructure managers, and other professional segments ▶ Interaction with the funding agencies could also be interesting, bringing them on board with the project (within the activities of WP3) 	<p>NOVA in collaboration with the partners ASTP and EARMA (responsible for WP3)</p>

Task 2.2 - Survey, gap analysis and recommendations to fulfil the training and networking needs identified

OBJECTIVES

- ▶ Identify training, networking, mobility and funding gaps for the RM community across the ERA, considering also those segment- and country-specific.
- ▶ Provide recommendations that could support the creation of a Europe-wide training and networking scheme in the future

Connection to other RM Roadmap work packages and tasks

The methodology defined for this task starts with the development of a survey targeted to the RM community. Considering that a survey is also planned for WP1 - [Task 1.1 Mapping RM Value Chain](#), a single survey will be developed to answer both inquiries.

Considering that the survey will be disseminated in the Knowledge and Community Platform, articulation with EARMA and Crowdhelix in [Task 4.6 Knowledge and Community Platform \(KCP\)](#) will be important.

Even though NOVA is not on the list of participants in WP3, the objective to provide recommendations will only be fulfilled if collaborating with EARMA in WP3 - [Task 3.4. Drafting of the Roadmap to Improve the RM System in Europe](#).

RM Roadmap partners involved

Leader: NOVA

Partners: HETFA, ASTP

Synergies with other actions and initiatives

- ▶ foRMAtion Intellectual Output 1 – mapping training offers
- ▶ Research Administration as a Profession (RAAAP) survey results, in particular regarding the mapping of skills and competencies
- ▶ CARDEA work on mapping and disseminating training/ networking/ mobility/ funding opportunities
- ▶ EARMA Professional Development and Recognition Committee (PDRC)
- ▶ Other initiatives identified during the project

METHODOLOGY WITH CALENDARIZATION

ACTIVITY	START-END
<p>Desk research on existing surveys already developed with similar aims (namely, RAAAP and CARDEA for the RMA topic, but also other surveys to map training needs and gaps in other fields)</p>	<p>Nov 2022 – Dec 2022</p>
<p>Online survey to complement the mapping of the training needs and the training gaps in the different RM communities, as well as to map trainers and their interest in collaborating in joint training (for inputs to Task 2.3).</p> <p>The questions related to WP2 will be integrated into a single survey targeting the RM community from all ERA, so all tasks below will be articulated together with WP1 - Task 1.1, namely:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Elaborating on the main topics and questions of the survey ▶ Validate the ethics and compliance procedures with HETFA & NOVA ethics committees ▶ Compiling a list of people from different aspects/backgrounds for the testing ▶ Testing the survey ▶ Dissemination & running the survey ▶ Analysis of the survey 	<p>Nov 2022 – Jan 2024</p> <p>Nov 22 - Jan 2023 Jan – March 2023</p> <p>Mar - April 2023</p> <p>April- Jun 23 Sept - Nov 2023 Nov 2023 - Jan 2024</p>
<p>Taking into consideration 1) the preliminary report about the training/ networking & mobility/ funding patterns, trends and gaps (August 2023) and 2) the analysis of the survey (Jan 2024), only if needed, online interviews will be conducted to further understand the reasoning beyond the patterns, trends and gaps previously identified in their specific context (geographic and segment)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Participants will be selected based on the questions/ clarifications needed after the analysis of the report and survey ● Design the script, test the interviews, and invite interviewees ● Qualitative analysis of the results, namely using comparative analysis and cross-analysis with the quantitative results from the survey 	<p>Jan - March 2024</p>
<p>The first draft of recommendations for a future Europe-wide training and networking scheme</p>	<p>March-May 2024</p>

METHODOLOGY WITH CALENDARIZATION

ACTIVITY	START-END
<p>Engagement with the RM community, namely through the ambassadors and the KPC community, to foster discussion about the main results and, most importantly, about the recommendations for future Europe-wide training and networking schemes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Presentation & discussion: Ambassadors' meeting in Lisbon ● Presentation & discussion: Ambassador's online sessions ● Exploring the digital interaction possibilities with RMA Forums, questions/ simple, or creating a form in the platform allowing stakeholders to provide information. ● Presentation & validation of the "Recommendations for a future Europe-wide training and networking scheme" - Ambassador meeting in Brussels 	<p>March 2024 - May 2025</p> <p>March 2024</p> <p>From March 2024 onwards</p> <p>November 2024</p>
<p>Focus groups with high-level policymakers to present and discuss the recommendations - articulated with WP3</p>	<p>Date to be defined within WP3 activities</p>
<p>The final presentation of the "Recommendations for a future Europe-wide training and networking scheme" - Brussels stakeholders dissemination meeting & Online dissemination conference by EARMA online</p>	<p>June 2025</p>

Deliverables and outputs

- ▶ Survey to RM community [Sept 2023](#)
- ▶ Survey report with the main results [Jan 2024](#)
- ▶ Interview script [\(only if needed\)](#)
- ▶ Interview report [\(only if needed\)](#)
- ▶ Report on training gaps [March 2024](#)
- ▶ Policy briefing document providing recommendations for a future Europe-wide training and networking scheme (in articulation with WP3) [Sept 2024](#)
- ▶ At least one peer-reviewed publication related to the results of the desk research and survey about training opportunities, gaps and needs (in collaboration with WP1)
- ▶ Communications at Conferences [2024](#)
- D 2.3 - Report on the Professional Development Opportunities [Jun 2025](#)

Target audience and stakeholders

- ▶ RM community in the ERA, in particular:
 - RM Roadmap ambassadors
 - Training providers in RM topics
- ▶ RMA associations, networks and informal communities of practice
- ▶ Universities, research institutions, companies, or any other type of institution that is an employer of RM and that could promote internal opportunities for their RM community
- ▶ Funding agencies
- ▶ Policymakers at national (Ministries) and international (ERA + EU Policy)

RISKS AND MITIGATION PLANS

RISK	RESIDUAL RISK LEVEL	MITIGATION MEASURE	RESPONSIBLE FOR MITIGATION MEASURES
Exclusion of some professional roles within the RMA profession considering the broad definition of all the professionals at the interface of science	High level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Close collaboration with the partner ASTP to provide information on RMAs in innovation ▶ Mapping of other associations or initiatives that represent or work closely with science communicators, brokers, data stewards, infrastructure managers, and other professional segments 	NOVA in collaboration with the partners ASTP and EARMA (responsible for WP3)
The low number of responses	Medium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Setting a target number for responses ▶ Use the mailing list of EARMA 	NOVA with the support of the partners
Interlinkage with tasks Ambassador Network (task 3.3) and Knowledge and Community Platform (Task 4.6)	Medium	Calendarization in line with WP 1 and 2	NOVA and responsible partners for 3.3 and 4.6 (EARMA and Crowdhelix)

Task 2.3 Fostering the creation of communities of practice among trainers

OBJECTIVES

- ▶ Bring together the trainers and networking providers to exchange best practices, lessons learned and teaching tools, as well as promote the development and inclusion of collaborative international practices into existing training activities.

Connection to other RM Roadmap work packages and tasks

Mapping the trainers and their contacts in WP2 - Tasks 2.1 and 2.2 will be necessary to start developing the Community of Practice (CoP) of trainers.

Considering that many ambassadors will have already some level of expertise in providing training, it will be important to foster the participation of the network of ambassadors in the CoP dedicated to trainers. As such, collaborating with EARMA in WP3 - Task 3.3. Create Ambassador Network Outreach.

With this particular task, we aim also to foster the capacity-building of trainers and the development of training skills in communities or geographies lacking training opportunities (mapped in WP2- Task 2.2). This capacity-building approach is very closely related to the tasks and activities planned for WP2 – Task 2.4 RM community incubator: Fostering national and thematic communities (in Widening Countries) including research infrastructure.

Finally, considering that the CoP targeted for trainers will be developed in Knowledge and Community Platform, articulation with EARMA and Crowdhelix in Task 4.6 Knowledge and Community Platform (KCP) will be necessary.

RM Roadmap partners involved

Leader: NOVA

Partners: All

Synergies with other actions and initiatives

- ▶ CARDEA work on mapping and disseminating training/ networking/ mobility/ funding opportunities (possibly with the identification of trainers that could be invited to participate in the CoP)
- ▶ foRMAtion Intellectual Output 4 – Methodological guide for foRMAtion mentorship programme
- ▶ EARMA Professional Development and Recognition Committee (PDRC)
- ▶ ASTP Professional Development Committee
- ▶ Other initiatives identified during the project

METHODOLOGY WITH CALENDARIZATION

ACTIVITY	START-END
<p>Create and test the usability and online features of the Community of Practice in the KCP</p>	<p>Jan – March 2024</p>
<p>Invite the RM trainers to join in the CoP target to trainers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Open call in the KCP platform ▶ invitation to the trainers mapped previously in Tasks 2.1 and 2.2 ▶ Invitation to the ambassadors' network ▶ Invitation to the EARMA's and ASTP committees 	<p>April 2024</p>
<p>Organize an online kick-off of the CoP</p>	<p>May 2024</p>
<p>Co-create with the CoP an activity plan that could include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Informal regular meetings, every 2 months, with topics identified by the CoP ▶ Initiatives of international collaborative practices ▶ Initiatives of mentoring (trainers-trainers, students-trainers) ▶ Create a repository of open-access training resources with the participation of all CoP 	<p>May – Jun 2024</p>
<p>Develop the planned activities with and for the CoP</p>	<p>May 2024 – May 2025</p>
<p>Plan and produce dissemination outputs to showcase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ New training initiative fostered by the CoP ▶ List of open-access training resources 	<p>Sept 2024-Jun 2025</p>

Deliverables and outputs

- ▶ Minutes of all the CoP meetings, with the geographical coverage
[May 2024 – May 2025]
- ▶ Dissemination outputs (to be decided by the CoP)

Target audience and stakeholders

- ▶ RM community in the ERA, in particular:
 - RM Roadmap ambassadors
 - Training providers in RM topics
 - RMs willing to get started in providing training
- ▶ RMA associations, networks and informal communities of practice that provide training
- ▶ EARMA PDRC committee and ASTP Professional Development Committee (particularly for the sustainability of the CoP)

Main priorities for engagement:

- ▶ fostering the participation of participants from the WIDENING countries
- ▶ include training activities related to the different RMA segment

RISKS AND MITIGATION PLANS

RISK	RESIDUAL RISK LEVEL	MITIGATION MEASURE	RESPONSIBLE FOR MITIGATION MEASURES
Exclusion of some professional roles within the RMA profession considering the broad definition of all the professionals at the interface of science	High level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Close collaboration with the partner ASTP to provide information on RMAs in innovation ▶ Mapping of other associations or initiatives that represent or work closely with science communicators, brokers, data stewards, infrastructure managers, and other professional segments 	NOVA in collaboration with the partners ASTP and EARMA (responsible for WP3)
Activities are very much dependent on the engagement of the community	Medium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ The kick-off meeting will be organized by NOVA to provide already a structure for the CoP future activities ▶ Possible activities are already planned to promote engagement, based on expertise in developing similar communities of practice 	NOVA with the support of the partners
Low level of participation	Low	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Start engaging with the training providers since task 2.1 ▶ CoP will only kick-start when the KCP platform and the Ambassadors' network is established 	NOVA, EARMA and Crowdhelix, with the support of the partners

Task 2.4 - RM community incubator: Fostering national and thematic communities (in Widening Countries) including research infrastructure

OBJECTIVES

- ▶ Fostering national and thematic communities (in Widening Countries) including research infrastructure

Connection to other RM Roadmap work packages and tasks

The methodology used in this task is based on the INORMS model. Therefore, the results of the RAAAP Survey will be used to extract conclusions. Additionally, and based on the INORMS model, complimentary desk research will be conducted to identify communities which are less developed in RM.

Considering that a survey will also be developed in **WP1 – Task 1.1. Mapping RM Value Chain**, and **WP2- Task 2.1 Analysis of existing training, networking and funding per segment of the RM community & creation of an open smart database, Task 2.2 Survey, gap analysis and recommendations to fulfil the training and networking needs identified**, a single survey will be conducted to address this issue as well. Moving a step forward, this task will advise on the next steps for community building of these communities linking with experts from communities in other countries.

For this, it will be important to foster the participation of the network of ambassadors, thus collaborating with EARMA **WP3- Task 3.3. Create Ambassador Network Outreach**. Under this task, the ambassadors will receive a role on the knowledge and community platform and receive training on community building and facilitation to be able to build or strengthen their community (WP2).

Therefore, there is a direct connection between the two WPs/tasks. Additionally, it is also important to leverage the results from **WP2 – Task 2.3 Fostering the creation of practice among trainers**. Finally, to foster the community CHX Platform under WP4, **Task 4.3 Collaborative Virtual Ecosystem: Research Managers Helix development and management** and **Task 4.4. Outreach Activities** will be leveraged.

RM Roadmap partners involved

Leader: CYI

Par NOVA, ASTP, UNAE

Synergies with other actions and initiatives

- ▶ RAAAP Survey results, especially regarding mapping needs, challenges, and gaps.
- ▶ Formation
- ▶ BESTPRAC
- ▶ Leiden Group
- ▶ Other initiatives identified during the project

METHODOLOGY WITH CALENDARIZATION

ACTIVITY	START-END
<p>Identification of the EU countries where the RMA profession is less mature, as well as the RMA segments that are less developed/ less known, by developing desk research and considering the results from past surveys (such as RAAAP, CARDEA and RM Roadmap surveys)</p>	<p>Aug - Nov 2023</p>
<p>One-to-one consultations with Ambassador Network (WP3) to identify any additional community gaps on thematic/segments and validate/complement the findings of the desk research. Emphasis will be given on widening countries and thematic/segments related to research infrastructures</p>	<p>Dec-Mar 2024</p>
<p>Identification of the existing RMA associations/networks in Europe with a collection of good practices in the development of national RMA associations/networks. This will be done by developing desk research (in particular considering the information collected in the Emerald Handbook of RMA globally) and engaging with the different RMA associations (in articulation with EARMA)</p>	<p>Mar-May 2024</p>
<p>Design a "business model template for RMA associations to guide evaluating what type of organization is appropriate in any given setting and the steps needed to accomplish it</p>	<p>Jun-Sep 2024</p>
<p>Engage with the RM community via Knowledge and Community Platform (WP4), to foster discussion about results and most importantly to gather feedback on recommendations/advice on next steps for community building in the identified thematic/segments with specific attention to research infrastructures.</p> <p>This task will be achieved by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Analysing the participation/engagement of RMs from the Widening Countries in the different thematic/ segment communities of the Knowledge and Community Platform ▶ Fostering the development of communities which are less developed in RM via the Knowledge and Community Platform ▶ Create a CoP dedicated to fostering the development of new RM communities, promoting engagement with RM leaders, in particular in the Widening countries, and promoting discussions and training with experts that can advise on community building. ▶ Consider the possibility to create a form in the online platform where stakeholders/ ambassadors can provide information (WP3) ▶ Leverage the different activities/meetings of ambassadors (WP3) ▶ Consider any other strategy that can be explored in collaboration with NOVA (WP leader) 	<p>Sept 2024-Jun 2025</p>

Deliverables and outputs

- ▶ Results of desk study and consultation (could be included in Deliverable 2.3)
- ▶ Recommendations with next steps for community building

Target audience and stakeholders

- ▶ RM Community, especially in widening countries, i.e. RM Roadmap ambassadors
- ▶ RMA organisations and informal RMA networks/communities
- ▶ RMAs specialised in Research Infrastructures

RISKS AND MITIGATION PLANS

RISK	RESIDUAL RISK LEVEL	MITIGATION MEASURE	RESPONSIBLE FOR MITIGATION MEASURES
A low number of responses, especially from Widening Countries	Medium to High	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▶ Setting a target number for responses▶ Leverage the ambassador network to secure responses	Cyl in collaboration with NOVA (WP leader) and support of other partners

MAPPING THE TRAINING, MOBILITY, NETWORKING AND FUNDING OPPORTUNITIES FOR RESEARCH MANAGERS IN EUROPE

This online template part of the European-funded project **RM ROADMAP**, particularly contributing to the WP2 task that aims at **mapping training, mobility, networking and funding opportunities** targeted to Research Managers across Europe. As such, our goal is to collect information about all available opportunities that are:

- ▶ Targeted to research managers (RM)
- ▶ Frequent opportunities (in opposition to isolated actions that may not be available in the future)
- ▶ Open for participation (in opposition to opportunities only open to RM from a particular institution)

The information retrieved will be used to disseminate these opportunities to the RM community in an **online and openly available dissemination tool/ dashboard**.

It will take 30 minutes of your time. It is divided into 5 categories: (1) Training activities, (2) Mobility opportunities, (3) Networking activities, (4) Funding schemes, and (5) Research Managers Networks. You may fill in the online template multiple times with the different opportunities you find relevant.

There are a few concepts we used in the online template we think are important to clarify:

* The definition of **Research Managers (RM)** in the current mapping exercise covers the different areas of specialization of these professionals working in both Research Performing Organizations, Research Funding Organization, and other (private companies, NGOs), including tasks as (but not limited to):

- | | |
|-------------------------|--|
| ▶ Pre-award | ▶ Policy |
| ▶ Post-award | ▶ Infrastructure data |
| ▶ Innovation | ▶ Management |
| ▶ Science communication | ▶ Research assessment |
| ▶ Outreach/community | ▶ Researcher development/ talent development |
| ▶ Impact | ▶ Lab management |
| ▶ Ethics | |

Regarding the 5 categories we will in this mapping exercise, please find the following explanations and examples:

1. Training activities: training courses, modules, degrees, programmes, etc.
2. Mobility opportunities: learning or professional mobility programmes for peer learning, job shadowing, internships, etc.
3. Networking activities: activities that may include training and mobility, but that the main aim is to provide networking opportunities for the participants. For example: Annual meetings of the RM associations, conferences targeted to RM-related topics, thematic groups, etc.
4. Funding schemes: funding programmes or opportunities that support RM professional development, such as mobility programmes, support to participate in events or in trainings, open applications for projects target to RM topics, etc.
5. Research Managers networks: that include formal and informal associations, platforms and communities of practice. For thematic groups that are part of an association, please include it in "networking opportunities".

If you have any doubt where your opportunity fits in, don't worry that we will revise all contributions and, if necessary, change the category accordingly.

Thank you!

*** Indicates a mandatory question**

EMAIL *

Country of working * (Mark only one)

- | | | |
|--|-----------------------------------|-----------------------------------|
| <input type="radio"/> Albania | <input type="radio"/> Iceland | <input type="radio"/> Poland |
| <input type="radio"/> Austria | <input type="radio"/> Ireland | <input type="radio"/> Portugal |
| <input type="radio"/> Belgium | <input type="radio"/> Israël | <input type="radio"/> Romania |
| <input type="radio"/> Bosnia and Herzegovina | <input type="radio"/> Italy | <input type="radio"/> Serbia |
| <input type="radio"/> Bulgaria | <input type="radio"/> Kosovo | <input type="radio"/> Slovakia |
| <input type="radio"/> Croatia Cyprus | <input type="radio"/> Latvia | <input type="radio"/> Slovenia |
| <input type="radio"/> Czech Republic | <input type="radio"/> Lithuania | <input type="radio"/> Spain |
| <input type="radio"/> Denmark | <input type="radio"/> Luxemburgo | <input type="radio"/> Sweden |
| <input type="radio"/> Estonia | <input type="radio"/> Moldova | <input type="radio"/> Switzerland |
| <input type="radio"/> Finland | <input type="radio"/> Montenegro | <input type="radio"/> Turkey |
| <input type="radio"/> France | <input type="radio"/> Netherlands | <input type="radio"/> UK |
| <input type="radio"/> Germany | <input type="radio"/> Northern | <input type="radio"/> Ukraine |
| <input type="radio"/> Greece | <input type="radio"/> Macedonia | <input type="radio"/> Other: |
| <input type="radio"/> Hungary | <input type="radio"/> Norway | |

What type of opportunity do you want to include? (Mark only one)

- Training activity
- Mobility. opportunity
- Networking activity
- Funding scheme
- RM Networks

1. TRAINING AVAILABLE FOR RESEARCH MANAGERS (RM) IN ERA

This section is dedicated to identification of existing training offer for Research Managers and Administrators.

1.1 Title of the training *

1.2 URL to the page of the training

1.3 Since when is this training opportunity available for Research Managers? *

(Mark only one).

- This is the first time this training is organized
- For less than 1 year
- For the last 2 -3 years
- For more than 5 years
- For more than 10 years

1.4 Who is the course for?

Identification of the level of study and experience of the targeted Research Managers

1.4.1 Level of study of target audience *

(Select all that apply)

- Continuing professional training
- Undergraduate student
- Postgraduate student
- Master student
- PhD student
- PhD holder

1.4.2 Professional experience in RM. *

(Select all that apply)

- None
- Eginners (1-2 years experience)
- Early-career(2-5 years experience)
- Mid-level (5-8 years experience)
- Senior (> 8 years experience) open to all levels of experience

1.5 Characteristics of the training

(Mark only one).

1.5.1 Please indicate the geographical coverage of the training *

(Mark only one)

- Local
- Regional
- National
- International

1.5.1.1 Please indicate the region and/or country and/or countries covered *

1.5.2 Language *

1.5.3 Format *

(Mark only one)

- Online
- Blended
- In-person

1.5.4 Mobility (spending time in another institution) *

(Mark only one)

- Includes mandatory mobility
- Includes optional mobility
- Does not include mobility

1.5.5 Please indicate the total length of the training *

(Mark only one)

- Short (less than 1 week)
- Medium (1 weeks to 6 months)
- Long (more than 6 months)
- Self-paced / self-study

1.5.6 Total hours of training *

1.5.7 Frequency *

(Mark only one)

- On request
- Annual
- Biannual
- Not defined
- Other:

1.5.8 Please indicate the starting date of the training.

(Example: January 7, 2019)

1.5.9 Please indicate the ending date of the training.

(Example: January 7, 2019)

1.5.9.1 If you don't know yet the start and end date, or if the training duration does not fit this description, please provide more information.

1.6 Training description

1.6.1 Please indicate the areas in RM covered by the training. *

(Select all the corresponding boxes that apply)

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="radio"/> Pre-award | <input type="radio"/> Infrastructure data |
| <input type="radio"/> Post-award | <input type="radio"/> Management |
| <input type="radio"/> Innovation | <input type="radio"/> Research assessment |
| <input type="radio"/> Science communication | <input type="radio"/> Researcher development/ Talent development |
| <input type="radio"/> Outreach/community | <input type="radio"/> Lab management |
| <input type="radio"/> Impact | <input type="radio"/> Leading a team/ Office |
| <input type="radio"/> Ethics | <input type="radio"/> Other: <input type="text"/> |
| <input type="radio"/> Policy | |

1.6.2 Please provide a short description of the training *

(Up to 1000 characters; include the list of the main learning outcomes, outline of topics and a brief description about the learning experience)

1.6.3 Please indicate the skills developed by attending the training *

(Up to 1000 characters; including soft skills and technical skills)

1.6.4 Evaluation of the participants *

(Mark only one)

- Mandatory
- Optional
- Not applicable

1.6.5 Description of the evaluation process *

(Up to 1000 characters; include requirements of attendance, evaluation criteria and instruments, etc.)

1.6.6 Is the training certified? *

(Select all that apply)

- None
- Certification of participation
- Provides ECTS
- Provides Degree
- Micro-credentials
- Other:

1.6.6.1 If the training provides a Degree, indicate what type

(E.g. Bachelor, Master, PhD, Post-graduation, etc.)

1.6.6.2 If the training holds an accreditation, which institution accredits the training?

1.6.7 Accessibility of training materials *

(Mark only one)

- Openly available online (all available)
- Partially available online (only some available)
- Not available online
- Not needed
- Other:

1.6.7.1 If available online, please indicate the URL

1.6.8 Training funded by (if applicable)

1.6.9 Is there funding available to attend the training?

(Mark only one)

- No
- Yes

1.6.9.1 In case there is funding available, please provide more information (requirements to apply/get the funding and/or URL)

1.7 Conditions for participation

1.7.1 Is the enrollment in the training subject to application and selection process? *

(Mark only one)

- No
- Yes

1.7.1.1 If yes, please provide a list of requirements or selection criteria

1.7.2 Cost *

(Mark only one)

- Free
- Not Free

1.7.2.1 If not free, please indicate the cost of the training

(In local currency of the training)

1.8 Follow-up activities

(Indicate if, after the training, some “follow-up options” are foreseen, such as networking initiatives, alumni association, mentorship programmes...)

1.9 Entity(ies) providing the training

1.9.1 Training provider *

(Select all that apply)

- University
- Research performing organisation
- RMA Professional organisation
- Funding agency
- Public administration entity
- Consultancy/ Training company
- Non-governmental entity
- Other:

1.9.2 Please provide additional details about the organization providing the training (name, city, country and general contact) *

2. MOBILITY SCHEMES AVAILABLE FOR RESEARCH MANAGERS (RM) IN ERA

This section is dedicated to identification of existing training offer for Research Managers and Administrators.

2.1 Title of the mobility scheme *

2.2 URL to the web page of the mobility scheme

2.3. Since when is this mobility opportunity available for Research Managers? *

(Mark only one).

- This is the first time this mobility scheme is organized
- For less than 1 year
- For the last 2 -3 years
- For more than 5 years
- For more than 10 years

2.4 Who is the mobility for?

2.4.1 Level of study of target audience *

(Select all that apply)

- Continuing professional training
- Undergraduate student
- Postgraduate student
- Master student
- PhD student
- PhD holder

2.4.2 Experience in RM of the target audience *

(Select all the corresponding boxes that apply)

- None
- Beginners (1-2 years experience)
- Early-career(2-5 years experience)
- Mid-level (5-8 years experience)
- Senior (> 8 years experience)
- Open to all levels of experience

2.5 Characteristics of the mobility

2.5.1. Geographical coverage of the mobility. *

(Mark only one).

- National
- International

2.5.2 In case of international mobility please indicate the country/ countries of origin.

2.5.3 In case of international mobility please indicate the country/ countries of destination. *

2.5.4 Please indicate the duration of the mobility in number of days *

(In case the duration is variable, please indicate the min and max of days of the mobility)

2.5.5 Please indicate the period in the year that the mobility takes place. *

(Select all that apply)

- Fall
- Winter
- Spring
- Summer
- N/A

2.5.6 Please indicate the starting date of the mobility.

Example: January 7, 2019

2.5.7 Please indicate the ending date of the mobility.

Example: January 7, 2019

2.5.7.1 If you don't know yet the start and end date, or if the mobility duration does not fit this description, please provide more information.

2.5.8 Please indicate the frequency of the mobility. *

(Mark only one).

- On request
- Annual
- Biannual
- Not defined
- Other:

2.6. Description of the mobility

2.6.1 RM areas covered in the mobility *

(Select all that apply)

- Pre-award
- Post-award
- Innovation
- Science communication
- Outreach/community
- Impact
- Ethics
- Policy
- Infrastructure data
- Management
- Research assessment
- Researcher development/ talent development
- Lab management
- Leading a team/ office
- Other:

2.6.2 Please provide a short description of the mobility *

(Up to 1000 characters; including the goals of mobility)

2.6.3 Please indicate the skills developed by attending the mobility *

(Up to 1000 characters; including soft skills and technical skills)

2.6.4 Evaluation of participants *

(Mark only one).

- Mandatory
- Optional
- Not applicable

2.6.5 Please provide more information on the description of the evaluation process *

(Up to 1000 characters; including requirements of attendance, evaluation criteria and instruments, etc.)

2.6.6 Is the mobility certified? *

(Select all that apply).

- None
- Certification of participation
- Provides ECTS
- Micro-credentials
- Other:

2.6.7 If the mobility holds an accreditation, which institution accredits the mobility?

2.6.8 Please provide more information on the accessibility of the support materials. *

(Mark only one).

- Openly available online
- Partially available online
- Not available online
- Not needed
- Other:

2.6.8.1 If available online, please indicate the URL

2.6.9. Mobility funded by (if applicable)

2.6.10 Please indicate if there is funding available to participate the mobility *

(Mark only one).

- Yes
- No

2.6.10.1 In case there is funding available, please provide more information

(Requirements to apply/get the funding and/or URL)

2.7. Conditions for participation

2.7.1 Is the mobility subjected to applications and selection process? *

(Mark only one)

- Yes
- No

2.7.1.1 In case you replied yes, please provide a list of requirements or selection criteria

2.8 Please indicate the cost of the mobility *

(Mark only one).

- Free
- Not Free

2.8.1 If not free, please indicate the cost of the mobility (local currency of the mobility).

2.9 Follow-up activities

(Indicate if, after the mobility, some “follow-up options” are foreseen, such as networking initiatives, alumni association, mentorship programmes...).

2.10. Entity providing the mobility

2.10.1 Please indicate the entity providing the mobility.

(Select all that apply)

- University
- Research performing organization
- RMA Professional organization
- Funding agency
- Public administration entity
- Consultancy/ Training company
- Non-governmental entity
- Other:

2.10.2 Please provide additional details about the organization providing the mobility (name, city, country and general contact) *

3. NETWORKING OPPORTUNITIES AVAILABLE FOR RESEARCH MANAGERS (RM) IN ERA

This section aims at identifying the networking activities available for Research Managers that are not training nor mobility opportunities.

Examples of networking activities are the annual meetings organized by RM associations, COST Actions meetings and other networking meetings and conferences organized with the aim of providing networking opportunities for Research Managers.

3.1 Please provide the title of the networking activity *

3.2 Please provide the URL of the networking activity

3.3 Since when is this networking opportunity available for Research Managers? *

(Mark only one).

- This is the first time this networking activity is organized
- For less than 1 year
- For the last 2 -3 years
- For more than 5 years
- For more than 10 years

3.4 Who is the networking activity for?

3.4.1 Please indicate the level of study of the Research Managers eligible for the networking *

(Select all that apply)

- Continuing professional training
- undergraduate student
- postgraduate student
- master student
- PhD student
- PhD holder
- Other:

3.4.2 Please indicate the experience level in RM *

(Select all that apply)

- None
- Beginners (1-2 years experience)
- Early-career(2-5 years experience)
- Mid-level (5-8 years experience)
- Senior (> 8 years experience)
- Open to all levels of experience

3.5 Characteristics of the networking

3.5.1 Please indicate the Geographical coverage of the networking *

(Mark only one)

- Regional
- National
- International

3.5.1.1 Please indicate the region and/or country and/or countries covered

3.5.2 Please indicate the format of the networking activity *

(Mark only one)

- Online
- Blended
- In-person

3.5.3 Please indicate if it includes a mobility *

(Mark only one)

- Includes mandatory mobility
- Includes optional mobility
- Does not include mobility

3.5.4 Please indicate the length of the networking activity *

(Mark only one)

- Short (less than 1 week)
- Medium (1 week to 6 months)
- Long (more than 6 months)
- Other:

3.5.5 Please indicate the frequency of the networking activity *

(Mark only one)

- On request
- annual
- biannual
- not defined
- Other:

3.5.6 Please indicate the starting date of the networking activity

Example: January 7, 2019

3.5.7 Please indicate the end date of the networking activity

Example: January 7, 2019

3.5.8 If you don't know yet the start and end date, or if the networking duration does not fit this description, please provide more information.

3.6 Description of the networking

3.6.1 Please indicate the RM areas covered in the networking activity *

(Select all that apply)

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="radio"/> Pre-award | <input type="radio"/> Infrastructure data |
| <input type="radio"/> Post-award | <input type="radio"/> Management |
| <input type="radio"/> Innovation | <input type="radio"/> Research assessment |
| <input type="radio"/> Science communication | <input type="radio"/> Researcher development/ talent development |
| <input type="radio"/> Outreach/community | <input type="radio"/> Lab management |
| <input type="radio"/> Impact | <input type="radio"/> leading a team/ office |
| <input type="radio"/> Ethics | <input type="radio"/> Other: <input type="text"/> |
| <input type="radio"/> Policy | |

3.6.2 Please provide a short description of the networking activity *

(Up to 1000 characters; include the goals of networking activity).

3.6.3 Please indicate the skills developed by attending the networking activity *

(Up to 1000 characters; including soft skills and technical skills).

3.7 Conditions for participation

3.7.1 Is the enrollment in the networking activity subjected to application and selection process? *

(Mark only one)

No

Yes

3.7.2. In case you replied yes in the previous question please provide a list of requirements or selection criteria

3.7.3 Please indicate in case the networking activity has a cost *

(Mark only one)

Free

Not free

3.7.4 In case the networking activity is not free, please indicate the cost (in local currency)

3.8 About the networking activity

3.8.1 Please indicate the entity organizing the networking activity *

(Select all that apply)

- University
- Research performing organisation
- RMA Professional organisation
- Funding agency
- Public administration entity
- Consultancy/ Training company
- Non-governmental entity
- Other:

3.8.2 Please indicate more details about the network (name, city, country, general contact) *

3.8.3 Please indicate the accessibility of the supporting materials provided during the networking *

(Mark only one)

- Openly available online
- Partially available online
- Not available online
- Not needed

3.8.3.1 If available online, please indicate the URL

3.8.4 Please indicate the funding source of the networking activity (if applicable) *

3.8.5 Is there funding available to participate in the networking activity? *

(Mark only one)

- No
- Yes

3.8.5.1 In case you replied yes in the previous question, please provide us more information of the requirements or URL *

4. FUNDING SCHEMES AVAILABLE FOR RESEARCH MANAGERS (RM) IN ERA

4.1 Please indicate the title of the funding scheme *

4.2 Please indicate the URL of the funding scheme

4.3 Since when is this funding opportunity available for Research Managers? *

(Mark only one).

- This is the first time this funding is available
- For less than 1 year
- For the last 2 -3 years
- For more than 5 years
- For more than 10 years

4.4 Who is the funding opportunity for? *

(Mark only one).

- Individual grant (if it will benefit one single individual)
- Institutional grant (if it will benefit a group of individuals/ an institution)

4.5 Who is eligible to apply? *

(Mark only one).

- Open to any applicants
- Members only
- Employees only
- Other:

4.6 Level of study *

(Select all that apply).

- Continuing professional training
- Undergraduate student
- Postgraduate student
- Master student
- PhD student
- PhD holder

4.7 Please indicate the level of experience in RM *

(Select all that apply).

- None
- Beginners (1-2 years experience)
- Early-career(2-5 years experience)
- Mid-level (5-8 years experience)
- Senior (> 8 years experience)
- Open to all levels of experience

4.8 Characteristics of the funding scheme

4.8.1 Please indicate the type of funding scheme *

(Mark only one).

- Fellowship
- Work contract
- Project grant
- Mobility grant
- Event organization grant
- Prize/distinction
- Other:

4.8.2 Please indicate the amount of the grant (if applicable)

4.8.3 Please indicate the geographical coverage of the funding. *

(Mark only one).

- Regional
- National
- International

4.8.3.1 Please indicate the region and/or country and/or countries covered *

4.8.4 Please indicate the frequency of funding opportunity *

(Mark only one).

- On request
- Annual
- Biannual
- Not defined
- Other:

4.9 Description of the funding scheme

4.9.1 Please indicate the geographical coverage of the funding. *

(Mark only one).

- Pre-award
- Post-award
- Innovation
- science communication outreach/community
- impact
- ethics
- policy
- infrastructure data
- management
- research assessment
- researcher development/ talent development
- lab management
- leading a team/ office
- Other:

4.9.2 Description of the funding scheme *

(Up to 1000 characters; include the funding goals).

4.10 Conditions for participation

4.10.1 Please provide a description of the eligibility rules *

(Up to 1000 characters; include the funding goals).

4.10.2 Please indicate the deadline for the submission of application *

4.11 About the Funding provider

4.11.1 Please indicate the type of funding entity *

(Select all that apply).

- Public funding agency
- Private foundation
- Company
- NGO/charity
- Professional association/network
- Other:

4.11.2 Please provide details of the funding entity (name, city, country and general contact) *

5. RM NETWORKS AVAILABLE FOR RESEARCH MANAGERS (RM) IN ERA

5.1 Name of the RM Network *

5.2 URL to the page of the RM network *

5.3 Starting year *

5.4 Type of RM network *

(Mark only one).

- Professional formal association
- Informal Association/ network
- Informal Community of practice
- Other:

5.5 Main objectives *

5.6 Please indicate the RM areas covered in the RM network *

(Select all that apply).

- Covers all topics related to RM (if selected this option, don't need to select the others below)
- Pre-award
- Post-award
- Innovation
- Science communication
- Outreach/community
- Impact
- Ethics
- Policy
- Infrastructure data
- Management
- Research assessment
- Researcher development/ talent development
- Lab management
- Other:

5.6.1 If your network covers a more specific area not included above, please describe it here.

For example: pre-award RM working only in European funding

5.7 Geographical scope *

(Mark only one).

- Regional
- National
- International

5.7.1 Please indicate the region and/or country and/or countries covered *

5.8 Brief description of the most relevant activities *

(Suggestion: focus on the activities opened for new comers participation).

5.9 Does participating in the RM network has a cost? *

(Mark only one).

- Free
- Not free / requeres membership

5.9.1 Please include more information about the cost/ membership fee *

5.10 Please provide the contact details of the RM Network *

Personal data and GDPR

Apart from the e-mail address, no other personal data was collected in this online template. Also, the e-mail contacts were only collected in case further information or clarifications are needed in order to correctly disseminate the information you have registered in your answer.

As an end result, we aim to develop an online tool/ dashboard where all the information related to the training, mobility, networking and funding opportunities will be openly available to all Research Managers across Europe. No personal information will be made available referring to the information provider.

If you have any question and/or feel it is important to clarify something before submitting your answer, please contact the NOVA team responsible for this online template:

Cristina Oliveira

coliveira@novaims.unl.pt

Ana Carrapato

ana.carrapato@cria.org.pt

Carolina Varela

carolina.varela@eua.eu

Diana Campelo Delgado

dianacampelo@fcs.unl.pt

Margarida Trindade

margarida.trindade@itqb.unl.pt

Statement of consent

(Select all that apply).

I have read the above information and feel that I understand the aim of this online template well enough to make a decision about my involvement. By clicking here, I am agreeing to the terms described above.

WORK PACKAGE 2 - TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT

Geographical Coverage	Country	Training Opportunity
International		The Virtual International Convention for Research Administrators
International		International Basics for Research Administrators (IBRA) workshop
International		EMBO Laboratory Leadership Course (we also offer courses on project management, negotiation, and self-leadership)
International		Research Project Management
International		European Research And Transfer Management 2023 Course
European		EURESTMA European Research and Transfer Management
European		Executive Masters' in Management of Research Infrastructures
European		Fundamentals of Technology Transfer
European		Research & Development Agreements
European		Marketing and Business Development
European		Creating Successful Spinouts
European		Organising Your Own KTO for Growth and Success
European		Fundamentals of Academic Consultancy
European		Software Specific Challenges in Technology Transfer
European		Knowledge Exchange in Social Science, Humanities and Arts
European		Negotiation Skills for KTOs
European		Financial Tools for KTOS
European		Technology Licensing
European		Research and Development Collaborations
European		Certificate in Research Management - CRM
European		Early Stage Research Administrators Masterclass, ESRAM
European		V4 Training for Research Project Managers

National	Bosnia and Herzegovina	Project management and administration
National	Germany	Master of Public Administration (MPA) Wissenschaftsmanagement
National	Germany	Weiterbildung Zertifikat EU-ReferentIn Forschung (EU consultant certificate/in research)
National	Germany	Research and Project Management
National	Germany	Wissenschaft im Dialog courses in science communication
National	Germany	RP Kompakt
National	Germany	RP Start
National	Germany	RP Aktiv
National	Germany	Introductory courses into EU Funding plus several advanced courses on interacting with Brussels and implementation issues like financial and legal questions in EU-Funding
National	Germany	Zertifikatsprogramm Wissenschaftsmanagement (Certified programme "Science Management")
National	Hungary	Research and Innovation Manager
National	The Netherlands	ARMA-NL Professional development training
National	Norway	Competence program for research administration - introduction
National	Norway	Competence program for research administration - advanced
National	Norway	Leadership seminar for RMA leaders
National	Poland	Akademia Managera projektów Horzontu Europa (Academy for Horizon Europe's project managers)
National	Portugal	Master in Science Communication
National	Portugal	O Essencial da Gestão de Dados de Investigação
National	Portugal	Webinar b-on
National	Portugal	Formação PUBIN
National	Portugal	Formação RCAAP
National	Portugal	Formação CIÊNCIAVITAE
National	Portugal	Rede de Promotores CIÊNCIAVITAE
National	Portugal	Pós-graduação em Políticas e Gestão de Ciência e Tecnologia (Post graduation in Science and Technology Policy and Management)
National	Portugal	Masters in Innovation and Research for Sustainability
National	Portugal	Curso de Gestão de Projetos Científicos em Saúde
National	Portugal	Training Course in Research Ethics/Integrity
National	Portugal	Research Data Management Course
National	Slovak Republic	National infodays - Horizon Europe
National	Spain	Knowledge Transfer: Fundamental Concepts and Practical Cases

National	Spain	Diploma de Experto en Promoción y Gestión de Programas y Actuaciones Internacionales de I+D+I
National	Switzerland	Newjoiner's training (modular)
National	Switzerland	Legal and Finance in Horizon
National	Switzerland	Communication
National	Switzerland	How to organise work and build resilience (3 modules)
National	United Kingdom	Certificate in Research Management Foundation
National	United Kingdom	Certificate in Research Management Advanced
National	United Kingdom	Developing a research strategy
National	United Kingdom	Post-Award Finance Induction - London
National	United Kingdom	Raising The Quality Of Research Proposals – Live Interactive Webinar
National	United Kingdom	Embedding Impact Into Bids: Supporting Impact In Development
National	United Kingdom	Supporting Research Proposals
National	United Kingdom	Developing Post Award Structures And Processes
National	United Kingdom	Research Management: Building Relationships, Increasing Our Influence
National	Ukraine	Knowledge Security, Research Vetting, and Cyber Security Course for Ukrainian Scientists

Table Training Opportunities
Total: 67

Geographical Coverage	Country	Mobility Opportunity
European		Knowledge valorization, TT, IPR and Spin-off creation
European		EARMA Awards Committee
National	Germany	ERA Fellowships Science Management
National	United Kingdom	ARMA Study Tours
National	Switzerland	Euresearch Network Exchange

Table Mobility Opportunities
Total: 5

Geographical Coverage	Country	Networking Activities
International		Working groups on Responsible Research and Innovation of the WBC-RRI.NET project (focused on Western Balkans)
International		Conferência Lusófona de Ciência Aberta (ConfOA)
International		Annual Meeting of the Society for Research Administrators International
National	Croatia	Yearly conference for RM managers in Croatia
National	Denmark	Networking activities organized by the Ministry of Higher Education and Science within EUDKSUPPORT and EU Erfa
National	Finland	Research Service Days (in Finland)
National	Finland	Annual Research Service Days
National	Germany	KoWi Annual Conference on EU Research & Innovation Funding
National	Germany	Networking activities within FORTRAMA , Wissenschaftsmanagement and Wissenschaftsmanager München
National	Germany	KoWi Annual conference on EU research and innovation funding
National	Norway	Narma annual conference
National	Portugal	Jornadas FCCN
National	Portugal	Fórum GDI - Gestão de Dados de Investigação
National	Portugal	Grupo de Trabalho A - Repositório de Dados: Tecnologia, organização e certificação (Fórum GDI)
National	Portugal	Grupo de Trabalho B - Formação e competências para a Gestão e Dados FAIR (Fórum GDI)
National	Portugal	Grupo de Trabalho C - Políticas, estratégias e recomendações GDI (Fórum GDI)
National	Portugal	Semana do Acesso Aberto (Portugal)
National	Republic of Ireland and Northern Ireland	Irish Knowledge Transfer Association Annual Conference
National	Romania	Meeting with the NCP and the support centres for R&D projects financed under Structural Funds
National	Switzerland	Network Day / Network Retreat
National	Switzerland	Monday Meeting
National	Switzerland	Spotlight on L/F
National	Switzerland	Dreiländertreffen der EU-Referenten
National	The Netherlands	ARMA-NL online and face-to-face network opportunities.
National	United Kingdom	ARMA Annual Conference
National	United Kingdom	ARMA (UK) Special Interest Groups

Table Networking Activities

Total: 25

Geographical Coverage	Country	Funding Schemes
International		Travel grants to ARMA-NL/EARMA/INORMS conferences
European		ERASMUS+ staff exchange mobility scheme
European		Twinning Bottom-Up
European		ERA Talents
European		Maire Curie Staff Exchanges
European		Excellence Hubs
European		Dissemination and Exploitation Support Facility
European		European Excellence Initiative
European		Support for the professionalisation of research management
European		Experimentation and exchange of good practices for value creation
European		Capacity building on Intellectual Property (IP) management to support open science
European		Programme level collaboration between national R&I policy-makers
European		Supporting the network of National contact points (NCPs)
European		Exploitation and valorisation of results relevant for the ERA Policy Agenda
European		Laying the groundwork towards Europe-wide citizen science campaigns
European		The future of research ethics review in the changing research environments
National	Albania	Scientific Research Infrastructure for HEI

Table Funding Schemes

Total: 17

Geographical Coverage	Country	Research Managers Networks
International		PM2 Alliance
Internacional		AUTM
Internacional		International Network of Research Management Societies (INORMS)
Internacional		NCURA
Internacional		NORDP
Internacional		SRAI
Internacional		RItrainPlus
Internacional		ENRICH in LAC is the European Network of Research and Innovation Centres and Hubs in Latin America and the Caribbean
Internacional		International Federation of Inventors Associations (IFIA)
European		Open Access Research Infrastructure in the Western Balkans Support Programme
European		NAAC Networks
European		MCAA Research Management Working Group
European		European Association of Research & Technology Organisations (EARTO)
European		European Association of Research Managers and Administrators (EARMA)
European		European Industrial Research Management Association (EIRMA)
European		European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI)
European		European Citizen Science Association (ECSA)
European		ASTP
European		Technology Transfer Inter-Regional Association (TTIRA)
National	Austria	Austrian Universities' Research Administrators and Managers (AURAM)
National	Belgium	Reseau LiEU
National	Belgium	Belgian Association of Research Managers and Administrators in European funded projects (BE-ARMA)
National	Belgium	Tech Transfer Offices Flanders (TTO Flanders)
National	Belgium	Hub.Brussels/ NCP Brussels
National	Bulgaria	Bulgarian Network of Technology Transfer (BNTT)
National	Bulgaria	Bulgarian Research and Education Network (BREN)
National	Croatia	Croatian KT Network (informal)
National	Czech Republic	Transfera
National	Czechia	CZARMA (Czech Association of Research Managers and Administrators)
National	Denmark	EU-DK Support

National	Denmark	EU-ERFA Networking Group
National	Denmark	Danish Association of Research Managers and Administrators (DARMA)
National	Finland	Finn-ARMA
National	France	Reseau C.U.R.I.E
National	France	Réseau SATT
National	France	Research Network on Innovation (RNI)
National	France	CAP Recherche
National	France	Association Française pour l'Information Scientifique (AFIS)
National	France	French association of science journalists (AJSPI)
National	France	French NCP Research Infrastructures
National	Germany	TransferAllianz
National	Germany	Netzwerk Wissenschaftsmanagement (Scientific Management Network)
National	Germany	Research and Transfer Management Network (FORTRAMA)
National	Germany	EU Liaison Office of the German Research Organisations (KOWI)
National	Greece	Praxi Network
National	Hungary	Technology and Knowledge Transfer Forum of Hungarian Universities (ETTF)
National	Iceland	Technology Transfer Office Iceland (TTO Iceland)
National	Iceland	Icelandic Association for Research Managers and Administrators (Ice-ARMA)
National	Ireland	Irish Knowledge Transfer and Innovation Group - (IKTIG)
National	Italy	Italian Research Managers
National	Italy	Network for the enhancement of research (Netval)
National	Italy	GdL CODAU Ricerca
National	Italy	Research Managers and Administrators (RMA) in Italia
National	Italy	Formicablu
National	Italy	Italian Association of Science Journalists (UGIS)
National	Italy	Science Writers in Italy (SWIM)
National	Italy	E.C. Partners
National	Italy	Italian Research Staff Association
National	Italy	SIMA (Società Italiana di Management)
National	Italy	Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea (APRE)
National	Italy	L'Agenzia per la valutazione del sistema Universitario e della ricerca (ANVUR)
National	Lithuania	Informal TT network Lithuania
National	Norway	FIN Foreningen for innovasjonsselskaper i Norge
National	Norway	ISPIM - International Society for Professional Innovation Management

National	Norway	Norwegian Network for Administration and Research Management (NARMA)
National	Poland	KRAB - Krajowa Rada Koordynatorów Projektów Badawczych UE
National	Poland	PACTT (Polish Network of Academic Technology Transfer Centres)
National	Poland	IP Management Poland
National	Poland	Polish Association of University Knowledge Transfer Companies (PSC)
National	Portugal	Informal Portuguese KT Network
National	Portugal	Platform at the Interface of Science (PIC)
National	Portugal	Algarve Systems and Technology Partnership Association (Algarve STP)
National	Portugal	SciCom PT: Rede de Comunicação de Ciência e Tecnologia de Portugal
National	Scotland	Registered Technology Transfer Professional (RTTP)
National	Serbia	Informal TT network Serbia
National	Slovenia	KO_sRIS II
National	Slovenia	Association of Technology Transfer Professionals of Slovenia (SI-TT)
National	Spain	RedOTRI
National	Spain	Redtransfer
National	Spain	Research Managers Network CARMA
National	Spain	La Asociación Catalana de Comunicación Científica (ACCC)
National	Spain	Asociación Española de Comunicación de Cultura Científica e Tecnológica
National	Spain	Asociación Galega de Comunicación de Cultura Científica e Tecnológica
National	Spain	Unique Science and Technology Infrastructures Roadmap (ICTS)
National	Spain	Fundación Andaluza para la Divulgación de la Innovación y el Conocimiento – DESCUBRE
National	Spain	CRUE: Conferencia de Rectores de las Universidades Españolas
National	Spain	CRUE - Red de Unidades de Gestión de la Investigación (Red UGI)
National	Spain (Catalonia)	CARMA - Research Managers network in Catalonia
National	Sweden	Swedish Association of Research Managers and Administrators (SWARMA)
National	Switzerland	Swiss Technology Transfer Association (swiTT)
National	Switzerland	Euresearch
National	The Netherlands	Dutch KT Network
National	The Netherlands	Association of Research Managers and Administrators in the Netherlands (ARMA-NL)
National	Turkey	USIMP- University Industry Collaboration Centres Platform of Turkey

National	Turkey	University-Industry Collaboration Centers Platform of Turkey (USIMP)
National	Turkey	Research Administrators Workshop
National	United Kingdom	ARMA (UK)
National	United Kingdom	PraxisAuril
National	United Kingdom	Association for Project Management (APM)
National	United Kingdom	Professional Research Investment and Strategy Manager (PRISM)

**Table Research Managers Networks
Total 99**

Total Opportunities: 213